

Figure 1: Passport Authentication (Schaedler, René, 2021)

Can Platform-Based International Police Collaboration Simplify the Authentication of Identity Documents?

Stefan Gabriel

Degree Dissertation submitted as part of the requirements for the MSc in Business Administration at the School of Business, Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts

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Student: Stefan Gabriel, stef@ngabriel.ch
Supervisor: Dr. David Griesbach, david.griesbach@hslu.ch
Client: OVD Kinegram AG, Zählerweg 11, 6300 Zug
Dr. Andreas Schilling, andreas.schilling@kinegram.com

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Abstract / Management Summary

This dissertation seeks to find out if platform-based international police collaboration can simplify the authentication of identity documents. To answer this question, it assesses the success factors of platforms through the perspectives of stakeholders and derives concrete use cases for platform-based collaboration. It is significant because police officers often lack the education and experience to authenticate foreign identity documents and on average, a forged document causes a damage of 55,000 €. The dissertation concludes that most success factors foster platform-based collaboration and that three concrete use cases for platforms emerged.

Identity document fraud is a problem because fake IDs are used for minor and crime. Especially young police officers with low exposure to foreign documents struggle to authenticate IDs. An in-depth literature review about platforms was conducted to provide a theoretical base about platforms, markets, and success factors in nine dimensions. The preliminary analysis concluded that there is no established collaboration platform to authenticate ID documents for international law enforcement and that no previous research investigated whether it does make sense to use some kind of platforms in that case. This qualitative research obtained data through 24 expert interviews and three written contributions, to explore the problem from the perspectives of four different stakeholders. The data was then analysed thematically to assess the success dimensions and uncover three concrete use cases. The dissertation revealed that platforms would bring benefits to international law enforcement because police officers would be able to become more autonomous, frictions could be lowered, efficiency improved, and process times reduced. Document experts would be able to provide important consulting services remotely, although they would not be able to provide final authenticity assessments through a platform. A document authentication platform could be extended to other user groups such as municipalities, airlines, banks, and car rentals to prevent economic damage and collect insights about series of fake IDs. The dissertation is limited to 11 European countries and between a small sample set of one to eight participants per country. While the results are meaningful from the perspective of stakeholders, it is not generalizable for international law enforcement in general.

Keywords: platforms, collaboration, success factors, use cases, law enforcement

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List of Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
APAC	Asia-Pacific
B2B	Business-to-Business
B2C	Business-to-Customer
BAZG	Bundesamt für Zoll und Grenzsicherheit
BAMF	Bundesamt für Migration und Flüchtlinge
C2C	Customer-to-Customer
DPI	Dots per Inch
EMEA	Europe, Middle East and Africa
EMPACT	European Multidisciplinary Platform Against Criminal Threats
EU	European Union
EUCARIS	European Car and Driving License Information System)
FADO	False and Authentic Documents Online
FIELDS	Frontex INTERPOL Electronic Library Document System
G2G	Government-to-Government
G2B	Government-to-Business
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
ID	Identity Document
iFADO	Intranet False and Authentic Documents Online
IND	Immigratie- en Naturalisatiedienst
IT	Information Technology
LATAM	Latin America
IR	Infrared
JET	Joint Expert Teams
MRZ	Machine-Readable Zone
KRIPO	Kriminalpolizei (Criminal Investigation Department)
NA	North America
NATO	North Atlantic Treaty Organization
PRADO	Public Register of Authentic identity and travel Documents Online
PCC SEE	Police Cooperation Convention for Southeast Europe Secretariat
UV	Ultraviolet
UK	United Kingdom
SIENA	Secure Information Exchange Network Application
SIRENE	Supplementary Information Request at the National Entries
SLTD	Stolen and Lost Travel Documents

Preface

As I embarked on this journey of exploring police work and document authentication, I was initially overwhelmed by the intricacies of the subject matter. However, I was warmly welcomed by the passionate participants in this industry, who generously shared their knowledge and experiences. Their camaraderie and dedication ignited my curiosity and guided me throughout this research.

I extend my heartfelt gratitude to the participants who generously contributed their time and expertise, shaping the findings of this thesis. I am grateful for the confidence of my employer, OVD Kinegram AG, in my work and their sponsorship of this study. Special thanks go to Sandra Slavinec and Stefan Schindler for their invaluable assistance in participant recruitment. Lastly, I express my deep appreciation to my wife Manuela, whose unwavering support has been a constant source of strength over the last two years.

1 Introduction

Young street police members struggle to establish identities based on foreign, uncommonly presented identity documents. Reasons for this are their young recruiting age and a full schedule from their basic training (personal communication, Antonio, 2022). Swiss police determine on a cantonal level how much authenticity checking is left to the street police and when document experts must be called in. Time-consuming clarifications lead to delays for the checked person. People with well forged IDs may avoid arrest due to the lack of expertise of the police (personal communication, summer 2022).

Domestic police know their national identity documents, visas, and drivers' licenses well, but they may rely on knowledge from local or foreign document experts to determine authenticity of foreign documents. Due to a lack of an international collaboration platform, public instant messenger services are used to exchange questioned documents in some cases (personal communication, Antonio, 2022).

My central argument is, that platform-based collaboration is used in private economy (Bika, 2016), but there is no established collaboration solution for international law enforcement and the authentication of identity documents. Platform-based collaboration could enable the provision of relevant knowledge in real-time to the place of the event.

This dissertation seeks to assess the success factors and find concrete use cases for platform-based collaboration in international law enforcement authenticating identity documents. It does so by executing an assessment of the situation from different perspectives of the main stakeholders.

Previous studies and articles around use cases and factors linked to platform-based collaboration in the private sector suit well as a basic theoretical perspective. However, the international law enforcement is complex, thus available literature can only provide limited information on whether the same findings also apply in this case. This general aim is broken down into context specific objectives:

- Identify stakeholders that are involved in the process of identity document authentication
- Assess success factors of platform-based collaboration
- Find use cases for platform-based collaboration

The goal of this dissertation is to create relevant knowledge, document use cases for such a platform and derive recommendations about how to handle factors that influence the implementation of such a platform. Accordingly, the research question to be examined is as follows: **Can platform-based international police collaboration simplify the authentication of identity documents?**

This dissertation starts with an introduction into the relevance of identity documents in law enforcement, continues with an overview of platform economy and key aspects that are responsible for success and failures throughout the literature review. The methodology and procedures chapter elaborates how the study was conducted. The data obtained from the interviews is aggregated and structured in the results part, providing valuable insights about the importance, current collaboration, and environment of identity document authentication. Towards the end, the discussion and conclusion chapter summarized and critically reflects the results before an outlook with a hint of personal opinion is provided in the recommendations. Within the appendices, I provide further insights and raw data.

2 Literature Review

The main purpose of this literature is to introduce people from the law enforcement industry to platform economy and establish a sense of urgency for ID-authentication for other readers. The literature review consists of three main parts, covering (1) the relevance of ID-fraud and ID-authentication, (2) a brief introduction to platforms in general and (3) key aspects of platform economy. The literature review provides a holistic and informed review of the current research and literature. It crystallizes the knowledge gap that leads to the following Research Question: **Can platform-based international police collaboration simplify the authentication of identity documents?**

2.1 Relevance of Identity Document Fraud and -Authentication

In this first section I offer a general insight into the context of this work. First, I explain why the authentication of identity documents is an important and difficult task. Then, I elaborate why experts for ID-authentication are needed and how patrol police and criminal police interact in that case.

2.1.1 ID-Fraud is a Problem. A study of GreenhouseTreatment.com (*Fake ID Usage in the U.S. (Survey)*, 2019) revealed that most survey participants use Fake IDs to enter establishments or to purchase alcoholic beverages. Fake IDs can be associated with problematic alcohol use (Deegan & Kotchick, 2021). The detection of fake IDs became more important in the recent years because the production of such documents migrated to overseas. As a result, local police are practically unable to prevent the circulation of forged documents. (Brown, n.d.). The Bundeskriminalamt found out that the average damage of social benefits fraud with fake identities in 2018 was 55,000 € (*Home. Die-Dokumentenexperten.De*, n.d.).

“Sicherlich spielt es [die ID Fälschung] eine grosse Rolle beim Bereich der Organisierten Kriminalität, wenn es um Diebesbanden geht, um Schleusungskriminalität geht, möglicherweise um Menschenhandel / Zwangsprostitution, etc. aber wir sehen das eben auch bei einfachen Delikten wie Onlinebetrug, Fahrkartenbetrug etc. Wir sehen das da, ich sag’ mal bei ganz Grundlegenden Delikten wie jemand hat keinen Führerschein und versucht das zu verbergen indem er sich also einen gefälschten Führerschein versorgt.” (Certainly, it [the ID forgery] plays

a big role in the area of organised crime, when it comes to gangs of thieves, smuggling, possibly human trafficking / forced prostitution, etc., but we also see it in simple offences like online fraud, ticket fraud, etc. We see it in I say very basic offences like someone doesn't have a driving licence and tries to hide it by getting a fake driving licence.) (MDR Investigativ, 2021, sec. 82)

2.1.2 Police Organisations Divide Tasks. Because ID-authentication requires education and training, there is a general division of work between patrol police and criminal police. Patrol are generalists and can schedule checks by themselves. They handle emergency calls and make an initial assessment of situations. Their job includes taking immediate measures, stop suspects and secure evidence. In the criminal investigation department, police officers solve the crimes. They use technical tools to make traces visible, record facts of the crime and investigate thoroughly. (*Tätigkeiten - Tätigkeiten*, n.d.) There are slight differences in how the division of tasks is organized within different police units. The essential division between patrol police and criminal police is similar in most countries (personal communication).

2.1.3 Police Start Young with Little ID Experience. The minimum age to become a member of the police starts from 18 years and often includes a maximum age cap. Every canton in Switzerland may impose different requirements but in general, Applicants are accepted exactly from the end of the apprenticeship or from the middle school leaving certificate (*Polizei Schweiz Voraussetzungen*, 2019). The Zurich police require a minimum age of 20 years and a maximum age of 34 years (▷ *Eignungstest Polizei Zürich*, 2018). In Hessen, recruits are accepted from 19 years old (*Voraussetzungen*, n.d.). Spain accepts candidates from three-year Spanish university degree which equals around 18 to 19 years (*Spain | OSCE POLIS*, n.d.). That is why street police depends on criminal police to determine document authenticity.

«Wenn ich an meine Zeit zurückdenke, bevor ich hier angefangen hab - über fremde Dokumente weiss man nichts. Man weiss nicht, wie ein Führerschein aus der Tschechei aussieht; jetzt unser Nachbarland. Noch geschweige denn, wie ein Führerschein aus Haiti aussieht». (When I think back to my time before I started here - you don't know anything about foreign documents. You don't know what a driving licence from the Czech

Republic looks like; now our neighbouring country. Let alone what a driving licence from Haiti looks like.) (Bügler, n.d., sec. 129)

2.1.4 ID-Authentication is Not Easy. Identity document authentication requires experience which is only gained over time. To become a questioned document expert in Colorado, one has to have almost perfect vision, to hold a degree in forensic science and complete a structured training program of at least 24-months (*Careers in Questioned Documents | American Academy of Forensic Sciences, n.d.*). The national police education platform currently offers a course with a duration of 11 days to learn about security elements, paper, reproduction and more skills required to perform authentication tasks (*| KURSANGEBOT, n.d.*).

An ID authenticity check is split into two aspects. On one hand, the form (as in the paper, card, carrier or substrate) can be authenticated. On the other hand, the data from the personalisation can be verified (Bügler, n.d., sec. 166).

2.2 Brief Introduction to Platforms

This second section is aimed to introduce the reader into the basics of platforms, starting with definitions followed by characteristics of multi-sided markets, externalities and crucial steps during the launch of the platform.

2.2.1 The Word “Platform” has Many Definitions. The automotive industry uses the word to describe a modular hardware element which can be reused in differentiated products (Muffatto, 1999, p. 145). Rochet & Tirole (2003, p. 28)’s definition of a two-sided market includes different types of end-users, externalities, a transaction. Eisenmann et al. (2006, p. 4) describe platforms as “Products and services that bring together groups of users in two-sided networks”, providing infrastructure facilitating transactions for the groups. Evans and Schmalensee (2016, p. 16) introduce the term “Matchmakers” for platform but agree that matchmakers “operate a physical or virtual place that help the different types of customers get together”. Similarly, Parker et al. (2017, p. 5) include business-based and value-creating interactions between two parties but also add open, participative infrastructure with governance to achieve matches and facilitating exchange (of goods, services, social currency). Platforms have two or more sides and connect different customers (McAfee et al., 2018, p. 204). McAfee et al. (2018, p. 163) highlight the platforms’ economic benefits being free (almost zero marginal costs), perfect (through digital reproduction of

goods), and instant (through online distribution). Steinberg (2019, p. 1) extends digital platforms into social media-, communication-, commercial-, media-, software-, educational-, political- and business platforms. He explains that traditional business convert into platforms and new platforms are constantly added. Belleflamme & Peitz (2021, p. 11) get straight to the point: “A platform can be roughly seen as an entity that enables interactions between users so as to generate value from these interactions”.

2.2.2 Single-Sided and Multi-Sided Markets Connect Different Types of Customers. Evans and Schmalensee (2016, p. 15) explain the difference between single sided markets (such as traditional grocery store) and a two-sided markets (such as a restaurant booking platform) as follows: A single-sided market is defined as one entity selling goods or services to another. On two- or multi-sided markets, multiple types of customers interact with each other on attractive terms. Two-sided markets involve choices by market intermediaries who solve some kind of interdependence or externality between the groups (Rysman, 2009, p. 126). In addition to similar explanations, Belleflamme and Peitz (2021, p. 2) also mention network effects that arise through multi-sided markets.

Figure 2 N-Sided Markets (Own Illustration)

2.2.3 Positive and Negative Externalities Happen Around Platforms. Externalities are positive (desired) and negative (undesired) effects that happen around the main interaction of the platform. A participant benefiting from a previous

transaction, for example, a text-translation, would experience a positive externality. A person not directly involved in a transaction but paying costs toward it experiences a negative externality. For that they use an example of a person hearing noise while a gardener works for the neighbour (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 136) Parker et al. (2017, p. 162) agree and provide a short definition of externalities being spill-over costs or benefits to someone outside the interaction.

2.2.4 (Solving) the Chicken and Egg Problem. Evans & Schmalensee (2016, p. 71), Belleflame & Peitz (2021, p. 113) and Parker et al. (2017, p. 89) agree that a platform offers services for multiple groups of users and need a critical amount of each group to become attractive for others (see 2.3.2).

Figure 3 Critical Mass Frontier (Own Illustration)

Note. Adapted from “Matchmakers: the new economics of multisided platforms” by Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 78. Harvard Business Review Press.

To overcome this problem, Belleflamme & Peitz (2021, p. 113) propose to use the divide-and-conquer strategy where the user groups are asymmetrically charged for a transaction, even subsidizing one of both groups. This matches strategy number four from Parker et al. (2017, p. 89), which propose seven additional strategies:

1. Follow the rabbit: Use non-platform demonstration project to model success
2. Piggyback: Connect user base from different platform, stage value creation
3. Seeding: Create value units for a first set of users before others follow
4. Marquee: Attract key users through incentives
5. Single-side: Create value for one side first, add the other side later
6. Producer Evangelism: Win producers and let them bring their customers
7. Big-bang: Use push-marketing strategies for high volume and attention
8. Micromarket: Start with a set of already interacting groups, and scale later

2.2.5 Handling and Establishing Trust. Trust is a prerequisite for matchmaking and transactions between buyers and sellers from different groups (Belleflamme & Peitz, 2021, p. 124). The adverse selection problem with hidden information, or the moral hazard problem with hidden action can lead to asymmetric information. Parker et al. (2017, p. 162) state that information asymmetry, especially the principal agent problem in relation to pricing is a main reason for market failure. Kostova (2014, p. 20) explains this asymmetry through different experiences of participants, psychological backgrounds and histories.

Issues can be addressed with certifications or warranties, by insurance or grooming of the network (Belleflamme & Peitz, 2021, p. 125). Trust into network participants can be raised through matching algorithms and rating systems. It is the platforms job to create a favourable environment for user action by imposing trading rules and reducing transaction risks.

2.3 Key Aspects of Platform Economy

This chapter provides insights about platform economies. It is structured according to inductive coding which emerged while reading through the books.

2.3.1 There are Different Platform Types. Literature provides different dimensions of distinguishing platforms. While Belleflamme & Peitz divide by the groups being connected, Evans & Schmalensee chose to consider the sales channels.

Steinberg (2019, p. 95) divides platforms into three categories, which I find most useful for this dissertation:

- Product-technology platforms like hardware and operating systems
- Content-platforms where users collectively contribute
- Transactional/mediation platforms linking money, people and commodities

There are business-to-business (SAP), business-to-customer (Alibaba), customer-to-customer (Dating) or and peer-to-peer (sharing economy) platforms. They operate on for-profit or non-profit business models. Platforms can start as non-profit as monetization models emerge once the user base is big enough or the platform is sold. There are transactional (trade activities facilitating) and non-transactional (information exchanging) platforms. The Linux operating system is considered a platform because it allows developers to interact. (Belleflamme & Peitz, 2021, p. 38)

Belleflamme & Peitz (2021, p. 110) introduce enabling and controlling platforms: Enabling platforms enable service providers and customers to directly interact and the platform leaves control over provision of the transaction to the parties and controlling platforms control the transaction with its residual control rights. Evans & Schmalensee (2016, p. 107) extend the control platform as follows: Depending on the operators business-model, two-sided platforms can be vertically integrated (if the operator itself offers services to one user group and allows third-parties to participate) or hybrid for reselling purposes (if the platform just connects parties).

The enabling mode (platform) fares better in terms of motivation (including professionals to exert efforts) and adaption (letting professionals adjust their actions according to their private information). The controlling mode (vertical integration, resell) fares better in terms of coordination (internalizing externalities across professionals, goods and services) (Belleflamme & Peitz, 2021, p. 110)

Figure 4 Platform Types and Characters (Own Illustration)

2.3.2 Network Effects Create Value and Advantages. Network effects are the main source of value creation and competitive advantage in platform business. They represent value from one user to another (Parker et al., 2017, p. 17), (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 22). There is positive or negative impact from one group to another and one group can affect the same side (direct) or cross-side (indirect). Network effects do not just happen to be enjoyed by the platform – the platform takes ingenuity and effort to create and nurture them (Belleflamme & Peitz, 2021, p. 3) because indirect network effects will generally fuel sustainable growth of a platform (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 36). Indirect network effects require a certain ‘thickness’ of the market to get started but once they run, they make the groups demands interdependent (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 29).

The authors Belleflamme & Peitz (2021, p. 11), Evans & Schmalensee (2016, p. 22), Parker et al. (2017, p. 162), Steinberg (2019, p. 98) agree on four types of network effects and that it is the platform’s responsibility to handle them by encouraging positive effects and avoiding negative effects:

1. Same-side positive effects (more telephone users make the telephone more valuable for every telephone user, thus attracting more)
2. Same-side negative effects (more users of a ride hauling app such as Lyft or Uber increase the waiting time for each user to be picked up)
3. Cross-side positive effects (higher value of producers on a platform attract more consumers willing to buy and vice versa)

4. Cross-side negative effects (a search engine promoting too much sponsored results on result-page one may annoy the users)

Parker et al. (2017, p. 34) highlight that network effects are not the same as price effects, brand effects, or other growth-building tools. They must also not be confused with virality: While virality attracts users, network effects keep them on a platform.

2.3.3 The Platform Creates Value for its Users. Evans & Schmalensee (2016, p. 16) Rochet & Tirole (2003, p. 5) and Parker et al. (2017, p. 38) agree that platforms must facilitate interactions and transactions between different user groups by letting them find and connect to each other to fulfil a specific task (Heck & Vervest, 2007, p. 33). Platforms can create new effectiveness by aggregating unorganized markets (Parker et al., 2017, p. 72). They do so by actively managing network effects among the agents (Belleflamme & Peitz, 2021, p. 108) which ultimately brings supply and demand together (McAfee et al., 2018, p. 203).

An important train of is provided by Parker et al. (2017, p. 69): They suggest that a uncoupling of an asset from the value it creates allows it to work more efficiently and increases the value of the asset dramatically.

Evans & Schmalensee (2016, p. 36), McAfee et al. (2018, p. 376) and Parker et al. highlight the key value of a platform lowering friction, transaction- and coordination costs between the participants and McAfee et al. (2018, p. 259) add that the elimination of information asymmetries is essential value provided by the platform. Platforms can act as online-to-offline enablers, for example, driving more traffic to ID checkers' offices after an initial online-consultation (McAfee et al., 2018, p. 215). This conversion is on the other hand not even required because the platform enables the independent participants to work in their respective environment and to connect the capabilities from a distance (Heck & Vervest, 2007, p. 33). Sepuru et al. (2021, p. 324) say that organizational capacity is impacted through collaboration, because it establishes and transfers knowledge.

Belleflamme & Peitz (2021, p. 38) write that maximizing profits by charging buyers and sellers is the main objective of a platform in return of managing the group network effects (2021, p. 63; Parker et al., 2017, p. 108)

Parker et al. (2017, p. 110) differentiate between four categories of value:

1. Value which a customer accesses through the platform
(Such as videos on YouTube, apps on Android, courses on Skillshare)
2. Value of access to a community or market for the producer
3. Value of access to tools and services that facilitate interactions and remove friction – for consumers and producers
4. Value of access to mechanisms that enhance the quality of interactions as in having the right stage for the right people looking for the right products – for consumers and producers

2.3.4 Stakeholders and Actors Around the Platform Ecosystem. A platform is part of an ecosystem, which consist of people, businesses, institutions and other things that interact with each other (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 103).

Parker et al. (2017, p. 39; p. 135) name four main actors when it comes to running a platform. The main value exchange happens between consumer and producer but behind every platform are two more entities: The manager and the sponsor. Manager and sponsor are often the same entity, but a software development company may want to delegate the management role to someone who is close to the users. They recommended to have a single sponsor to avoid awkward decision-making, promote simplicity and easy use of technology.

Figure 5 Elements of Platform Networks (Own Illustration)

Note. Adapted from “Platforms, Markets and Innovation” by A. Gawer, 2009, p. 135. Edward Elgar Publishing.

McAfee et al. (2018, p. 267) introduce two subdivisions of producer. They differentiate between core (hired, skilled experts) and crowd (external knowledge' provided by 'new participants won by the internet and its technologies'). Within platforms, the core is chosen through rules and approval processes, by humans and groups who can object. The crowd is more impulsive than the core, of decentral nature and uncontrolled. They voice freedom of expression and innovation. Similar to McAfee, also Parker et al., (2017, p. 141) split developers into 'core developers', extension developers, and 'data aggregators'. Core developers gets the platform and deliver value through tools and rules to make core interaction easy. Extension developers add features and value to the platform and enhance its functionality and are normally outside parties, not employed by the management firm. The data aggregators improve algorithms by adding data points for the participants.

2.3.5 Technology and New Architectures Relaunched Platforms.

Matchmakers do the same old stuff but with new information and communication technologies which turbocharged the multisided platform model (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 198; Parker et al., 2017, p. 60). Essential drivers for this evolution are more powerful chips, the internet, world wide web, broadband communications, programming languages and operating systems and the cloud (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 40). Knowledge workers benefit from computers because the computers take over simple rule-based and logical work, giving them more resources to focus on their work. (McAfee et al., 2018, p. 46). Apart from the gained effectiveness, algorithms can exceed accuracy and results of human judgement because human judgement is influenced by biases that negatively affect decisions. The algorithms are only as good as the data they work with and as soon as companies or humans analyse a problem from different perspectives, they exceed the algorithms (McAfee et al., 2018, p. 77).

Systems should be built on the end-to-end principle which means that critical components should be built at the edge of the system, increasing routing options and improve data delivery rates. Only core functionality important to should be located in the core of the platform (Parker et al., 2017, p. 52). Different platform functionality should be built in a modular way to increase effectiveness. The platform as a whole will work through well-defined interfaces, connecting cleanly partitioned subsystems (Parker et al., 2017, p. 55).

Technology delivery valuable metrics over the lifetime of a platform. Metrics around the core interaction, such as liquidity, matching and trust support the start-up phase. During growth, insights around value creation such as size of user base, lifetime value and user conversion rate become more important. Once the platform is established, attention should shift towards identifying new functionalities and the strategy of competitors (Parker et al., 2017, p. 203). Insights lead to action, such as the implementation of dynamic pricing to overcome resource congestion (Rochet & Tirole, 2003, p. 997).

2.3.6 The Manager Facilitates Interactions. The platform manager has the main job of acquiring, activating, matching, and keeping (enough and the right) participants while removing unwanted parties to enable valuable transactions (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 30; McAfee et al., 2018, p. 204; Parker et al., 2017, p. 44; Rochet & Tirole, 2003, p. 29).

The manager considers the interest of all sides and balances trade-offs between volume and margins, making sure that every participant gets enough value from the interactions to nourish network effects (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 30; p. 57).

The manager takes over the role of an enabling host and is responsible for hospitality. This is achieved through the design of a great user interface and user experience. The platform must facilitate interactions by providing tools and rules in physical or virtual environments (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 36; McAfee et al., 2018, p. 204; Parker et al., 2017, p. 44)

Platforms operate in ecosystems or at least business environments. The matchmaker must pay a lot of attention to this environment and its surroundings which affect how easily participants get together (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 102). Pioneering platforms must understand the ecosystem and win its support to persuade participants into acting beneficial for the platform and more importantly for the ecosystem.

2.3.7 Well Begun is Half Done. Platforms must overcome the collective action problem which means that, especially in established ecosystems, multiple participants must take a leap at the same time to start the platform (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 115). A critical mass is required before network effects pull in further participants. It can jump-start interactions by providing in-house services for

early buyers until enough producers are onboarded (Belleflamme & Peitz, 2021, p. 131). It could start small by attracting few sellers to win buyers, which will then attract more sellers. The early adopters must generate optimistic expectation and feedback loops (Belleflamme & Peitz, 2021, p. 121).

In any case, it is recommended that the platforms start with the core interaction which is defined through participants, their value unit, and the filter. Iterative functionality increase is better than platform-by-design (which runs the risk of becoming overengineered and fails to evolve (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 178; Parker et al, 2017, p. 58). Failing to evolve through new functionality least to users abandoning the platform, given an alternative (Parker et al., 2017, p. 52). If there are two or more established alternatives, it will be difficult to build a new dynamic platform, due to first mover advantages and the-winner-takes-it-all markets (McAfee et al., 2018, p. 204).

2.3.8 Openness Towards Users, Suppliers, Providers and Sponsors.

Multisided platforms are situated within broader ecosystems of firms, governments, regulation, and other institutions and must get along with everyone. Ecosystems or their environment may be changed through the appearance of platforms. The platform therefore has to decide how many customer groups and sides it wants to serve (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 36). Many participants have governance systems with laws, enforcers and penalties which need to be considered to promote positive network externalities for direct and indirect ones and deter negative ones.

Every role can be more open or more restrict. Whereas Linux is open on all four levels (such as Sponsor, Manager, Consumer and Producer, recall 2.3.4), an iPhone is closed for every role except for the demand-side user (Gawer, 2009, p. 133).

“A platform is ‘open’ to the extent that. (1) restrictions are not placed on participation in its development, commercialization or use; and (2) any restrictions – for example, requirements to conform with technical standards or pay licensing fee – are reasonable and non-discriminatory, that is, they are applied uniformly to all potential platform participants” (Gawer, 2009, p. 131).

The amount of openness depends on the original design to be proprietary or shared platform. A proprietary platform, which is sponsored, managed and completely

controlled by one party can only become more open, whereas something completely open can only become more closed over time. (Parker et al., 2017, p. 154)

2.3.9 Governance of Power, Communities and Markets. Belleflamme & Peitz (2021, p. 219) only briefly discuss governance in the context of a sellers selling strategies. They propose that a matchmaker can make use of his power to limit the sellers' visibility of the buyers, by making them pay to access more sophisticated tools (like keyword-access for dynamic pricing of goods and services).

Evans & Schmalensee (2016, p. 137) compare multisided platforms to communities providing a place for participants to get together. They need rules to enforce a certain behaviour, because the behaviour of the users has an impact on the value of the matchmaker. Positive behavioural externalities should be nurtured, and negative externalities should be minimized by discouraging participants from behaving badly.

Parker et al. (2017, p. 182) state that governance is important to address the fact that free markets are prone to failures like information asymmetry, externalities, monopoly power and risk. They recommend designing basic governance tools such as laws, norms, platform architecture, and defined markets with care to encourage positive behaviours of participants incentivizing good interactions. Well-run platforms execute self-government following principles of transparency and participation. Belleflamme & Peitz (2021, p. 128) add cancellation policies, certification systems or even insurance to the toolkit supporting a minimum quality standard. Quality control is especially important with many new arrivals, as new sources of supply may have negative impacts without community-driven curation (Parker et al., 2017, p. 68). McAfee et al. (2018, p. 268) mention more traditional tools for self-government such as a board with approval processes and people & groups who can object decisions.

“Geeky leadership” can be used to manage crowds. This leadership style stands for openness, freedom to presuppose, self-organisation, verifiability, and clarity of goals for results. Geeky leadership does not solve all problems – it also requires tries, errors and luck for a platform to become successful. (McAfee et al., 2018, p. 289)

The managers of the platform motivate platform participants to collaborate, formulate targets, vision and strategies to shape a culture, values and many other essential tasks (McAfee et al., 2018, p. 376). Even if more and more digital-native

companies increase competition, companies remain efficient in handling inadequacies of contracts and will remain part of the economic landscape.

2.3.10 Strategies for Mutual Growth and Healthy Competition. Platform competition involve platform-against-platform, platform-against-partner, and partner-against-partner that must be accounted for. Strategic focusses must lie on cooperation and co-creation as well as improving relationships. Strategic goals can be multihoming-prevention, capturing value of innovation, leveraging value of information, and enhancing design. Winter-take-all markets exists and are driven by the four main factors: supply economics of scale, network effects, multihoming & switching costs, and lack of niche specialization. (Parker et al., 2017, p. 228)

2.3.11 Pricing and Business Models to Generate Revenue. Matchmakers work to make markets thick and to facilitate the interactions and matches on the platform. They must be compensated for their work (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 123). While a platform often offers free access to at least some functionality to build the network and convert the users to paying customers (Parker et al., 2017, p. 109), free (and negative) pricing can remain if one side is subsidized by the other participant (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 32)

Getting the pricing structure right is critical for both, getting started and to make sure it the platform is profitable in the long run. To achieve fair pricing, the platform has to balance the demands of multiple groups (Evans & Schmalensee, 2016, p. 36).

Belleflamme & Peitz (2021, p. 141) summarize two essential revenue models for platforms: there are fixed membership or subscription fees which are usually based on a recurring time period, and transaction fees which are usage fees for every transaction or commissions based on a transactions value.

Rochet & Tirole (2003, p. 15) have an excellent work about price elasticity and formulas which do not (at least yet) apply to this dissertation. They elaborate different dynamic pricing models, of which one is designed to achieve non-profit transaction fees, calculating dynamic “access fee” in a scenario where the other prices are set by the end users.

2.4 Why Digital Platforms Succeed or Fail

My initial literature research lead me to Özcan et al. (2022). They executed an extensive literature research through 73 peer-reviewed, English papers about success and failure factors of digital platforms. They identified 24 factors which were mentioned as success factor or as failure factor within the papers. Through paraphrasing, analysing, and clustering, they summarized the factors into nine dimensions (Özcan et al., 2022, p. 3). Those nine success and failure dimensions of digital platforms provide the structure for my results. Özcan et al. (2022, p. 4) also provide a table of how frequently the factors occur as success or failure factors. The first four dimensions account for 75% of success factors and 67% of failure-factors, hence I distinguish between “Major Success Factors” and “Minor Success Factors” within results (Appendix B).

Figure 6 Major and Minor Success Factors of Platforms (Own Illustration)

Note. Adapted from “Why do Digital Platforms succeed or fail? - A Literature Review on Success and Failure Factors” by Özcan, Leon; Koldewey, Christian; Duparc, Estelle; van der Valk, Hendrik; Otto, Boris; and Dumitrescu, 2022, p. 3. AMICS 2022 Proceedings.

2.5 Conclusion

There are many online services that claim being able to determine identity document authenticity. GBG promises to “keep your business save while swiftly verifying identity documentation” (*Forensic Document Examination Experts | GBG IDscan*, n.d.). IDScan.net offers a software development kit which can check an identity document against multiple light sources and uses more than 400 AI-powered security checks (Gillies, 2022). Verifai offers a tools that enable manual checks against a database of over 2,000 documents but no collaboration functionality (*Document Authentication*, n.d.). There are more solutions but most of them only offer software-based authenticity checks to companies in the private sector. The PRADO database is a collaborative platform from document experts around Europe which does contain information about all sorts of identity documents but it only acts as a library and does not provide ways for interactive collaboration between users and experts (*Startseite*, n.d.). Netherlands operates 4 regional ID desks which employ document experts. If a document looks suspicious, a merchant can contact the police, which will then contact those experts for further clarifications (Defensie, 2017).

From the information available and known to me at the beginning of this research I conclude that there is no standardized platform which enables patrol police and document experts to collaborate case-based on an international level in an quick and efficient manner. I will conclude the literature review in a topic-specific conclusion over the next three chapters to elaborate, why document authentication is important, how platforms work in general and why platform-based collaboration would be useful for international law enforcement.

2.5.1 Conclusion of Part 1: The Relevance Identity Document Fraud and Authentication. While ID fraud itself is already a felony, ID fraud is usually just one measure to cover up bigger felonies. Due to the organisation of the police organisations, collaboration between patrol police and document experts is needed and requires patrol police and document experts to collaborate. Especially younger members of the police are often on patrol duty and miss the experience to determine document authenticity and therefore rely on the document experts.

2.5.2 Conclusion of Part 2: Brief Introduction to Platforms. The literature reveals a communality over all different definitions of platforms: They may operate

online and/or offline, facilitate transactions and create value for multiple parties. There are single-sided markets (such as one party selling to another) or multi-sided markets. Patrol police (needing assistance) and document experts (offering knowledge) can be considered two parties. Patrol police does benefit from experience of document experts (positive externality). To get started, the platform needs customers (patrol police) and sellers (document experts) which leads to “the chicken and egg”-problem. That means, patrol police will not use the platform if there are no experts available. Experts on the other hand may stop offering their services if there are no requests from patrol police. Trust is crucial for international collaboration, which can be established through a trust mediator, bridging different backgrounds, education, experience, and procedures.

2.5.3 Conclusion of Part 3: Key Aspects of Platform Economy. There are different platform types, of which a transactional/mediation platform with an enabling character is favourable for ID authentication in law enforcement (2.3.1). Once a platform would attract critical mass, it could improve the value for its users by enabling positive network effects, attracting even more users of both parties (patrol police and document experts) (2.3.2). The main value proposition of an ID-authentication platform was increase of efficiency, lower friction, lower transaction- and coordination costs and a positive impact on organizational capacity (2.3.3). The stakeholders can roughly be reduced to four parties: (1) the sponsor of the technology, (2) the manager of the platform, (3) the consumer and (4) the producer. It can be thought of opening stakeholders such as sponsor and producer to the public, allowing external developers to provide add-ons or allowing other document authentication services to offer their services onto the platform to create extra functionality and value (2.3.4). Technological developments enable new kinds of platforms and automated decision making, matchmaking or algorithms further boost efficiency and interlink parties and metrics can establish transparency (2.3.5). The manager of the platform can be the same as the technology provider, but it is possible (and beneficial) to leave the role of the manager to a trusted party within the ecosystem of law enforcement (2.3.6). A core interaction should be defined first, interlinking a limited number of participants, before onboarding and scaling into further use cases and other parties (2.3.7). While law enforcement operates with known and trusted parties, but an open collaboration platform could to a certain extent also benefit other participants such as smaller police organisations, municipalities, or banks to jointly fight crime with fake IDs (2.3.8).

Platform governance through rules and regulations is crucial for successful operation across international law enforcement (2.3.9). It should be decided on a strategic level if and which platform should be used in the future (2.3.10). Transaction based pricing can increase cost transparency and reward the experts for their services. A transaction fee can cover development costs and compensate the matchmaker (2.3.11).

3 Methods / Procedures

My qualitative research combines two methods to obtain best possible results. It follows the structure of Mayring's seven steps as described by Shreibe! (2019) being (1) research question, (2) procedure, (3) coding, (4) assessment, (5) finish coding, (6) reliability check, (7) evaluation and interpretation. In addition, I consider elements of the methodology used by Terrill & Flitman (2004, p. 295) which follows the four steps being (1) preparation, (2) repertory grid interviews, (3) qualitative analysis and (4) secondary analysis with literature.

I choose Mayring's method because it is widely accepted in research and considers important aspects such as reliability and validity. From Terrill & Flitman's methodology, repertory interviews it improves validity as the research problem is investigated from four perspectives and three to ten participants per perspective. Instead of following up with a secondary literature analysis, I analyse the literature at the beginning and use the interviews to determine if the platform economy theory also applies for the law enforcement and ID authentication industry. This method suits the aim of the research, answer the research question and produces valid results.

The stakeholder analysis around the topic of identity document authentication from my client and me defined four roles with important perspectives towards the research problem (Appendix A). These four perspectives shall increase the work's credibility. These viewpoints can be distinguished by their nation of origin as well as their roles (Patrol police, document expert, strategy/executive, and service centers).

I created one interview guide per role by choosing questions which explore the nine success dimensions mentioned by Özcan et al. (2022, p. 3). I used Özcan et al.'s literature review to define four major factors (Governance, Stakeholder Management, Value Proposition and Strategic Management) as they collectively accounted for 75% of all mentions of success factors and 67% of all failure factors (Appendix B). I grouped the remaining five factors (IT Architecture, Marketing & Communication,

Enterprise Culture, Pricing Structure, Legislation & Regulation) as minor factors. The questions aim to find out whether the international law enforcement environment would foster or hinder the implementation of platform-based collaboration and to find out whether there are use cases for platform-based collaboration in that area. The number of questions per success or failure dimension are chosen in relation to the weighting of that given factor (Appendix D). The four interview guides can be found in Appendix E. The interview guides are reviewed by my client to improve reliability and validity.

With the help of a flyer (Appendix C) I started non-probability, purposive sampling through my professional network, looking for subject-matter experts that are defined through their experience, role and country. Further participants are acquired through chain referral, although I expected similar hurdles such as access to experts and the verification of their eligibility as described by Biernacki and Waldorf (1981). I tackle those issues by brief background research about the participants before I onboard them and furthermore give them the chance to introduce themselves at the start of an interview. I do not calculate the saturation point like Terril & Filtman did, but instead aim to get five or more representatives per group of participants to improve reliability of the study. The list of study participants can be found in Appendix F.

The participants of the study display a huge leap of faith into me and my work but also towards my employer and client OVD Kinegram. The participants work in a delicate and secretive industry and their willingness to take part in this study provides opportunity but also risk. After considering Saunders et al. (2015), I choose to give the participants the opportunity of participating anonymously by working with aliases. The raw data (recordings, transcripts, and coded texts) are only saved on devices with access protection, within encrypted volumes. Transcripts will only be shared upon request and approval of the concerning participant, except for one encrypted copy of the coded data delivered to the supervisor for quality assurance. The key to the data expires on 31 December 2023, see Appendix G.

Participants pick their preferred date, time, location, and language of the interview. I offer Swiss German, German and English to lower the chance of participant-side translation errors. Emergent research is supported using open, narrative, semi-structured interview guides. The research is conducted from the point

of view of a neutral, industry-independent student with wide knowledge about technology and platform-based economy and little knowledge of the ID authentication industry. The online interviews take place through Webex and are recorded. I offer phone call interviews as a fall-back. German and English interviews and transcribed automatically using sonix.ai. I transcribe interviews in Swiss German manually.

Consistency of evidence is supported through continuous analysis of the data (Appendix H) using the software MAXQDA. For the analysis of literature and primary data, I use a hybrid coding approach as explained in Grad Coach (2022). I analyse literature through inductive coding (Appendix I). For the primary data obtained through the interviews, I use Özcan et al.'s (2022, p. 3) nine dimensions as deductive categories (see chapter 2.4). I then added inductive in vivo and descriptive coding. André Gubser, my manager with similar experience and education, improved validity by coding two written contributions. The assessment of intercoder reliability can be found in Appendix K. The final coding table can be found in Appendix J.

From the coded data, I derive insights about the nine dimensions for the success and failure of platforms and identify use-cases for platform-based collaboration in the context of this dissertation. I compare the results against the existing theory developed in the literature review. I document the three most mentioned use cases as use case diagrams as described by Jacobson (2004, p. 211). The dissertation follows Gordon Millar's (2021) guide about writing dissertations.

4 Results

This section outlines the findings of the research, demonstrating the outcomes achieved through the data analysis and interpretation. The assessment of major and minor success factors for platform-based collaboration are grouped according to Özcan et al. (2022). Subsequently, the concrete use cases for platform-based collaboration are elaborated.

4.1 Assessment of Major Success Factors

The major success factors include Governance, Stakeholders, Value Proposition and Strategic Management. Value Proposition is included within the emergent cases and has therefore no independent chapter.

4.1.1 Governance: Operator, Approval, Trust, Rules, and Openness.

Thoughts about the preferred operator of the platform. The platform could be operated by a trustworthy outside company (EX08, ¶ 23) from the private sector or even state-owned (DE03, ¶ 38-40) because the EU orders services and IT infrastructure from third-party companies. (DE05, ¶ 56-57). It could be operated by any international reliable IT-partner contracted by the government (EX01, ¶ 41). It may make sense to create a new legal entity for the collaboration platform because some governments may be reluctant to work with existing companies (EX05, ¶ 95-99). Private companies may be more agile towards the needs of the users (EX04, ¶ 29-33), nevertheless, the EU should oversee decisions (EX04, ¶ 39-40). Although document experts do not want to be attached to just one company, their support is likely that the platform will be beneficial against document fraud (EX05, ¶ 101-103). Ownership of the product must be considered before working with private companies, because a software developed by a police organization may be used by themselves and others free of charge, whereas commercial applications imply license fees (EX08, ¶ 23). Any commercial entity could provide the technology (EX07, ¶ 57-58) but it seems unlikely that the technology providers also run the platform (EX07, ¶ 75-76). Collaboration with non-police companies and their employees which were not sensibilized against espionage led to bad experiences in the past. (EX08, ¶ 52-55)

An European platform could be run by Frontex (EX01, ¶ 23, EX08, ¶ 52-55) as Frontex previously already brought national activities to the EU area (DE06, ¶ 65). Frontex has the limitation, that its mandate is limited to exterior borders (EX07, ¶ 73-

74). There may be no need to search for a new operator as future developments of FIELDS or FADO (already operated by Frontex) may obviate the need for a new platform (EX10, p. 1-2)

The European union could be a desired operator because it already has member states (EX04, ¶ 29-33, SC03, ¶ 47). Europol (EX08, ¶ 52-55, PP01, ¶ 72, SC03, ¶ 47) and Interpol are preferred operators (SC03, ¶ 47) because of working colleagues in countries outside Europe or countries that are less open for platforms (EX03, ¶ 25). Europol is limited due to its mandate for serious crimes and fighting crime which excludes crime prevention. Interpol could operate on a global scale (EX07, ¶ 73-74) and has more members, but some may not be comfortable if Interpol would be managed by a director from a ‘unfavourable’ country’ (EX08, ¶ 52-55). An international platform could be run by the International Civil Aviation Organization (EX01, ¶ 23). Each continent may have their own decentral platform, which are interlinked (SC02, ¶ 50-51).

Most interviewees propose personal-network-based participant approval. “You have to start from a position of trust until it's proven otherwise.” (DE04, ¶ 51). The platform should leverage the existing network and grow through personal recommendations (DE07, ¶ 53-57) and work colleagues (DE02, ¶ 42). This leads to an internal list of trustworthy document experts (EX05, ¶ 19). Experts know each other or at least organisation they work for through previous collaboration (EX07, ¶ 70). Within the European Union and Schengen area, the network is established through the specialist board or high-level roundtable by Frontex (EX06, ¶ 27-29). “Some kind of committee” could approve individual members (DE06, ¶ 54). Authorities could select suitable employees with known expertise and adequate secrecy screening (EX07, ¶ 72) which conflicts with the statement of DE02, that a central administration is not able to assess a person’s role, education, and competence (¶ 42) but EX08 (¶ 43) thinks, it’s a central administrations job to verify the qualifications of the members – maybe with a second assessment from an inhouse expert (EX07, ¶ 72). The service center SC02 trusts experts who have completed training with them (SC02, ¶ 48-49). There must also be procedures to withdraw access to participants on misconduct (DE04, ¶ 46).

“Grundsätzlich ist die Plattform nur so viel wert, wie die Leute, welche die Beratung erbringen.” (Basically, the platform is only worth as much as the people who provide the advice.) (DE07, ¶ 53)

Participants must be fit for the job to establish trust. DE07 (¶ 53-57), DE06 and SC01 agree that skills and training are requirements to be fit for the job and competences could be proven by completing eLearning modules (DE06, ¶ 56) or trainings (SC01, ¶ 46). The Frontex high-level roundtable defines minimum standards for document and identity verification and related courses (EX08, ¶ 45). EX08 thinks, that it is not necessarily needed to prove expertise through an exam within the platform (¶ 46-47). An expertise certification would foster trust into the platform if the certification were retained through training, updates, and tests (EX05, ¶ 22-23). Only document experts who know the working environment of the officers who request assistance, have received a dedicated training and go regularly on mission to the operational areas to stay in touch with the realm of operations should offer their expertise (EX10, p. 2). While EX02 (¶ 18-19) and EX03 (¶ 20-23) rely on advice from police and document experts of the issuing country, especially because they have access to the local information systems, DE02 (¶ 78) said that document experts from a foreign border, where a certain other document is presented more frequently, can have more experience with given document. Experts trust each other if they know them personally (EX04, ¶ 23-24), can display the same level of authority in their field through the platform (PP02, ¶ 43-45, EX01, ¶ 20-21), even without disclosing their country of origin (PP02, ¶ 43-45). The platform should introduce different levels, for example “users” and “experts” to establish trust (EX01, ¶ 27). Transparency about the structure, and method of expert recruitment (EX03, ¶ 23-24) and about who processed an inquiry also supports trust (DE02, ¶ 65).

A strong link between participants and their organisation is encouraged. It must be ensured that participants belong to a police or customs authority (DE03, ¶ 36, EX01, ¶ 61, EX07, ¶ 25-56, SC03, ¶ 40-43, DE07, ¶ 58-59), ideally through country-wide police-participation (DE05, ¶ 35) or a trustworthy registration to establish a link between user and their organisation (SC02, ¶ 45, PP05, ¶ 37, EX01, ¶ 61). ICAO (Ex05, ¶ 13) or an administrator per country could approve the application of the person through their name, police ID, picture (EX03, ¶ 18-19) and their employment status (EX05, ¶ 13). In addition, a peer-confirmation-mechanism can be established

(EX03, ¶ 85-87) so that teams would share knowledge with trusted people (EX05, ¶ 11) who establish a link of trust through their local organisation and the national organisation they belong to (EX05, ¶ 19). According to EX10, any country who contributes with the same commitment as EU Member States and Schengen countries are considered trustworthy, although restrictions may remain (p. 1)

Users can be authenticated in different, trusted ways. Basic authentication (DE04, ¶ 73) could be available to the public without authentication, but upper levels (such as certified document experts) should require enrolment and authentication in the system (EX10, p. 1), through a login and password (DE08, ¶ 30-31, EX09, ¶ 29-30) or ideally through an Intelligent Access Management Tool, using autologin with existing credentials (SC01, ¶ 29) through official e-mail addresses (SC03, ¶ 40-43). Frameworks from existing solutions, such as FIELDS, may be expanded for the use case of the new platform (DE04, ¶ 44-45). The platform can be trusted if it is accessed through official, secure channels and after approval of the own administration (PP03, ¶ 37).

Rules for institutionalisation and collaboration. The platform can institutionalize international police interactions that already exist but are not yet managed by an administration (EX04, ¶ 73-76). Rules and regulations regulate the usage of public apps and data (DE06, ¶ 117) and how information can be exchanged. The absence of rules does not prevent activities taking place in wrong ways (EX04, ¶ 16). Access to different levels of information can be restricted: The European Commission and FADO Member States decide about European Information stored in FIELDS. (EX10, p. 1). Frontex has a rule set for usable and unusable information and its exchange (EX06, ¶ 29). If no common denominator is found, a platform can organize itself into smaller units (EX03, ¶ 82-87).

The platform should remain “ID” industry related. The company Document Authentication Services GmbH offers their services any company or (police) organisation (SC02, ¶ 46-47). The platform should be a private public cooperation, where the private sector is able to register as well (EX05, ¶ 86-94). This opinion is not shared by EX07, which agrees that the private sector may supply technology, but should not have access to data (¶ 57-58). A workaround may be a segmentation, where different entities share different levels of information (DE04, ¶ 68-69). EX01 would

grant access to organizations, as long it is ensured that forgers cannot join (§ 19). The JET Project is an example for an EU project where third countries of western Balkans or Schengen partners such as Switzerland can join as well (EX07, § 26).

4.1.2 Stakeholders: Management Team, Top-Level Support, Participants, and Potential Customers. *Stakeholders drawn from the interview material.* Over the course of this thesis, I have learned about different entities and country or even global entities. An overview, of these entities and possible stakeholders is visualized on the stakeholder map below, where stakeholders are placed according to their active participation (vertically) and their importance (horizontally). Accordingly, crucial stakeholders (towards the right) with high participation (towards the top) should be involved from the early stages of the platform development.

Figure 7 Stakeholder Map (Own Illustration)

Note. I placed the entities according to my subjective perception and the context they were mentioned in the primary data.

There are different opinions about the constellation of the management team.

Frontex made a lot of things easier in the past (DE06, ¶ 65) and should therefore represent the management team (EX04, ¶ 105, EX06, ¶ 96) with its Center of Excellence in Document Fraud (EX07, ¶ 78, EX08, ¶ 18). Being a private organization could be a problem for Frontex (EX03, ¶ 29). Any security authority with “certain qualification in the area” of identity verification and document authentication could be in the management team (EX08, ¶ 63-64).

The European Commission can be a part of the management team (EX04, ¶ 105) and the platform could be seen as an EU-project (EX05, ¶ 35) but EX05 (¶ 14-17) suggests that it should be international and bigger than the EU. Interpol should be included, and maybe even municipalities should be represented through their police organisations. EX03 (¶ 25) and EX10 (p. 2) agree that Europol and Interpol should be represented in the management team. EX10 would also include border guards and customs. EX03 (¶ 25) doubts that there will be a central administration and considers the exchange of personal data an obstacle for Interpol and Europol.

EX05 (¶ 13) suspect that ICAO is too big to provide the management team but also EX02 (¶ 21-24) mentioned ICAO because it has a board of all countries. It depends if the platform will be run as a federated system or centrally managed by just one organisation. Other compositions that were mentioned consisted of an “upper-level team which manages a contract of the various law enforcement officers from each country” (EX04, ¶ 28), a steering committee of the heads of the criminal investigation departments (DE07, ¶ 67) or an international organisation dealing with borders or identity issues (EX01, ¶ 47) with a strong lead and core team (¶ 63)

Top-management support is crucial. The heads of the border police must establish contacts on a higher level among the individual countries. The initiative must come from the head level (SC03, ¶ 55) but also politically desired (PP01, ¶ 37). In Switzerland, it will be a board of police commanders who will decide about the implementation of a platform (DE07, ¶ 107)

“Es müsste von ganz oben, von der Polizeiführung, muss so eine Plattform unterstützt werden, weil sonst wird es niemand verwenden.” (it [such a platform] would have to be supported from the top, from the police leadership, because otherwise nobody will use it.) (DE07, ¶ 107)

Everyone involved in the three-tier document authentication system or government departments should participate. The participants are not only limited to police (DE03, ¶ 36, DE05, ¶ 35, DE08, ¶ 28-29), second line (DE08, ¶ 28-29), and forensic experts (DE08, ¶ 28-29, EX01, ¶ 19, EX04, ¶ 43). Different government departments (DE04, ¶ 16) and counter fraud units (DE04, ¶ 16) should participate as well as border guards, customs (DE03, ¶ 36, DE04, ¶ 17, DE05, ¶ 35, EX04, ¶ 43) and federal offices without access to the police networks (DE02, ¶ 59, DE04, ¶ 16). Even manufacturers of software and components for identity documents should be considered participants (DE02, ¶ 46). There are also more sweeping participant formulations such as “NATO, Schengen or EU Members” (EX02, ¶ 15) and “Every law enforcement agency” (EX02, ¶ 53).

But there are undesired participants as well. Besides obviously undesirable participants such as identity card forgers and document forgers or their relays (DE03, ¶ 36) there are individuals with a negative mindset towards document authentication because they are using the niche of document authenticity to promote their career (DE02, ¶ 42). There are some Interpol member states which violate human rights (DE04, ¶ 43) or “Groups that we wouldn't like to join and of course, other groups wouldn't like us to join because they have a different way of looking at the world.” (EX02, ¶ 90). Considering a participation of security device manufacturers, some countries some have less strict rules regarding the copying of products which could lead to the sabotage of genuine industries (EX02, ¶ 13).

“We have had some [REDACTED] spies in the Netherlands that tried to [REDACTED]. These were people that were here on a diplomatic passport, so they had an official status. We couldn't arrest them. Yeah, you don't want to facilitate that kind of misuse of a status. So, you don't want to give them a platform where they can use all the information to create stuff for that kind of purpose.” (EX02, ¶ 27)

Valuable customer groups for a document authentication platform. Primary customers are police organizations (EX05, ¶ 17, EX07, ¶ 44, EX09, ¶ 28, SC03, ¶ 31), at least for the beginning (EX08, ¶ 62). The service should also be offered to customs and border guards (EX07, ¶ 44, SC03, ¶ 31), including external border controls or own standing corps (EX07, ¶ 78).

Municipalities were often mentioned as a client group (EX04, ¶ 96-97, EX05, ¶ 17, EX07, ¶ 65) in addition to migration offices (SC01, ¶ 10), Notaries (SC02, ¶ 19), foreigners' authorities (SC03, ¶ 31, EX07, ¶ 66), the driver's licence offices, (EX07, ¶ 65) and the registration office, weapons authorities, and consulates (EX07, ¶ 65-66).

“I see a great danger in identity fraud. When I apply for an identity card in Switzerland, I go to the canton. And there are often administrative employees who have little or no training. It's the same in Germany or almost everywhere in the world. I have the civil administration, the one that issues the documents, which are then genuine. This means that I see a great need to improve the possibilities for checking them, because as soon as the genuine document has been issued or obtained by fraud, I can check it at the border, and it will always be genuine.” (SC03, ¶ 43)

The private sector can also benefit and if fraud can be prevented, it does not cost the government that much (EX05, ¶ 86). Car rentals have a lot of damage when expensive cars are stolen through false identities (SC02, ¶ 21, EX08, ¶ 62). Banks and financial service providers (EX07, ¶ 86, EX08, ¶ 62, SC02, ¶ 21) as well as insurance companies (EX07, ¶ 68) and lawyers (EX08, Pox. 62) could be users of such a platform. Airlines are obliged to transport only properly identified passengers (EX07, ¶ 61), hence airline information desks are potential customers, too (EX08, ¶ 29).

4.1.3 Strategic Management: Activities, Value Proposition, Critical Mass, Launch & Growth, Goals, Prerequisites. *Strategic activities towards a platform for document authentication.* There is a project called JETS, “Joint Expert Teams” (Bundespolizei Karriere, 2021) launched by German “Bundespolizei” (Federal Police) (DE03, ¶ 48, DE05, ¶ 45, EX06, ¶ 80) and funded by the European Commission (EX10, p. 1). Frontex is a main player in documents industry, they work and investigate towards a “bigger format” platform (EX06, ¶ 96-98, ¶ 110-118, EX10, p. 1). The experience that Swiss DE07 (¶ 7) brought back after participating in a German “action week” started movement and Switzerland is investigating if the system should be copied (DE01, ¶ 27, DE07, ¶ 69) but there are no concrete plans yet (DE05, ¶ 45). The helpdesk itself operated through a helpdesk app which was in essence a customized messenger service that converted a request into an email. The e-Mail is then processed by experts based on a picture (EX07, ¶ 21). The project interlinks

document experts across EU countries (EX07, ¶ 25). Spain has copied the concept and runs a test themselves (EX07, ¶ 44). The FEDPOL in Switzerland is in the process of setting up such a helpdesk service for the cantonal police may later expand to customs and border guards. The French National Police wants to set up such a test at its premises. In the Netherlands, a helpdesk was already set up for the Dutch police (EX07, ¶ 44). Albania is also setting up “something” and in future, these helpdesks should be interlinked with each other (EX07, ¶ 46, EX08, ¶ 16, SC01, ¶ 20).

Austria operates helpdesk called “Polizei Kooperationszentren” (Police Cooperation Centers). They foster information exchange and document authenticity checks with neighbouring countries (DE06, ¶ 78). Germany has “Gemeinsame Zentren” (Joint Centers) not having a common platform yet (SC03, ¶ 51). They currently work towards a common multilingual form, for example English and Spanish to overcome language barriers (SC03, ¶ 51). Frontex is also considering setting up such a helpdesk (EX07, ¶ 70, EX08, ¶ 27). The commercial helpdesk SC02 is only active in German regions but plan to expand into regions with other languages as well. That requires document experts to master more languages (SC02, ¶ 55).

Regarding self-service portals, INTERPOL works together with Frontex to develop FIELDS (EX06, ¶ 32) to bring Frontex’ Quick-Check-Cards to the frontline. FADO is available in multiple countries but DE06 is not aware that one can request support through it (¶ 78). Germany is working on expanding the “Duderstadt model”, where registration authorities receive simple training of the tools, person comparisons, receive access to an e-learning platform and receive access to the helpdesk mentioned above (EX07, ¶ 65). Not all activities become known: EX03 (¶ 35) is not aware of any strategic activities towards an international platform for document authentication. Enforcement units may have platforms, but none of them are forgery related (PP02, ¶ 52) Front related employees tend to know little to nothing about ongoing strategic activities (PP03, ¶ 43-45, PP04, ¶ 44-45), but so does DE09 who doubts being in the right circle to know (¶ 70-71).

The platform should provide what the respondents describe as the "most important function. The most important feature would be the direct data query about name, ID card number, issue date and personal data (4.3.1) (DE01, ¶ 55, DE04, ¶ 71, PP04, ¶ 28) which would confirm a document’s (DE05, ¶ 51, PP03, ¶ 51) or person’s

existence (DE01, ¶ 55, DE05, ¶ 51) and maybe how the person looks like (DE01, ¶ 55). It should provide informational support (DE08, ¶ 39-40, DE09, ¶ 38-39).

Another option would be the Guided authenticity check (DE02, ¶ 69) which enables selectively, specifically asking questions, about a document (DE07, ¶ 81) it should give a definitive answer there and then (PP02, ¶ 61). Guided support on behavioural and identity issues would also be appreciated (SC01, ¶ 37)

The platform should make document experts more accessible to the patrol (DE01, ¶ 33) and provide timely contact options from the relevant country (DE03, ¶ 54). Personal contact (DE06, ¶ 87), not only of the specialist, but like a hub, would be valuable (EX06, ¶ 105). It should connect offices to answer and obtain questions about documents or their issuance (PP02, ¶ 63) or support foreign authorities (EX08, ¶ 70)

Thesis participants are eager to support a platform. Some have already participated in related projects (DE02, ¶ 65, EX02, ¶ 33, EX07, ¶ 45-46, DE09, ¶ 73) and everyone else would support activities as an early adopter (DE05, ¶ 49, DE06, ¶ 84, EX01, ¶ 39, EX03, ¶ 37, EX04, ¶ 78-79, EX05, ¶ 55-62, EX09, ¶ 37, PP02, ¶ 54, PP03, ¶ 47, PP04, ¶ 47, PP05, ¶ 51)

Opinions on launch and growth differ. While DE04 would start with data query and gradually add more features to build trust and move into a more collaborative workspace (¶ 71-73), DE06 would expand the FADO case (¶ 60). EX07 would multiply the helpdesk system throughout Europe (¶ 43-44). When asked if the system of Royal Marechausee could be expanded, EX02 declined due to congested resources, but would rather support Frontex growing into a federated platform through bilateral agreements (¶ 27, ¶ 35), starting with Europe and maybe America (¶ 92). EX08 and his team have a sophisticated proposal: Deploy it as an add-on to an existing app, introducing the new document authentication use case to document specialists and service multipliers, which would increase acceptance with users. Once it works in Germany, expand to Schengen members (EX08, ¶ 33) Start with simple use case of sharing information as Quick-Check-cards and build relations and tackle language barriers through AI (¶ 59-60)

The platform should be developed in private sector and then be expanded through the onboarding of different companies (EX05, ¶ 95-107). DE05 would start internationally coordinated, onboarding whole countries (¶ 35). Deployment could

start in one country, connecting different police organisations, for example Cantonal, municipal, and communal police forces (DE05, ¶ 37). EX01 would start with an international organization involved in border or identity issues, invite member states to shape development, specifying business needs, one anchor per country, to grow interest and trust (EX01, ¶ 47). Platforms depend on their reputation and should start small to make sure they work, before expanding with more users (SC03, ¶ 57).

The strategic goal of a platform is to reduce crime across borders through collaboration. The goal is to prevent cross border crime (EX02, ¶ 31, EX03, ¶ 39, EX04, ¶ 12, EX05, ¶ 52) and identity plus document fraud (DE04, ¶ 53, DE05, ¶ 69) through international cooperation and collaboration (EX02, ¶ 31) based on solidarity between colleagues (EX03, ¶ 39). The platform should help detecting patterns (EX01, ¶ 35) of the origin of fraud (EX05, ¶ 52) to start an investigation (EX01, ¶ 35) and stop it at an early level (EX05, ¶ 52).

An operative goal is to facilitate faster IDs authentication (DE08, ¶ 36, EX09, ¶ 35, SC01, ¶ 23) which speed up checks through law enforcement (EX10, p. 2), through quick answers of genuineness of document authenticity or information validity (EX04, ¶ 12). This facilitates border crossing and improves trust in private-commercial relationships which ultimately ensures public security, improves trust (EX10, p. 2) and leads to security and justice against criminal organization (EX04, ¶ 8)

Sharing of knowledge and know-how improves the learning curve of officers who are not document experts and enables exchange between about ongoing cases with document experts (EX10, p. 2, Ex01, ¶ 35). At the end the platform would work as an institutionalization of something that already exists between police (EX04, ¶ 73).

There are requirements for the approval of a platform. Before the platform can be built, it must be supported by the right organizations (EX05, ¶ 69) and a national or international organisation team must be assembled (EX08, ¶ 39) which will work with the right project management approaches (EX10, p. 2). Driving forces may be Frontex (EX07, ¶ 78), helpdesk operators or the head of “Referat 33”¹ (EX08, ¶ 17-18).

This team must define a clear business case (EX08, ¶ 39, EX10, p. 2) which includes processes, human and financial resources, and a clear strategy for sustainable

¹ “Referat 33, Kriminaltechnik, Erkennungsdienst und Urkunden der Bundespolizei” (Bundespolizeipräsidium Organisationsplan, 2022)

development of the service (EX10, p. 2). It must be established that the work becomes easier for frontline staff, and that there is an increase in document forgeries detection (DE05, ¶ 71).

Before data collection starts, a data protection impact assessment and a “Schutzbedarfsabklärung” (protection needs-assessment) should be carried out (EX08, ¶ 39). This provides the base for a uniform quality standard for the exchange of personal and biometric data between authorities (EX04, ¶ 85, EX08, ¶ 39, EX10, p. 2).

Data protection is a crucial prerequisite. For EX04, a guarantee for secure information management is a prerequisite to collaborate through a platform. Information should only be exchanged in a managed way (¶ 14-16). He suggests that constraints must be analysed beforehand, which data, for example the photograph of the owner of the document, can be shared (¶ 53). EX09 (¶ 32) sees no downsides in using platform-based collaboration if protected exchange of information is provided. EX10 (p. 2) agrees and stresses the fact that the problems around data protection shall be resolved in advance. EX03 (¶ 25) doubts that there will be a central administration of all personal data, but if there was one, it should be administered by Europol and Interpol. Greece is very strict with personal data and a platform would only be approved with appropriate security measures (¶ 37)

The work of the document experts is subject to data protection considerations and data protection guidelines. It must be clarified who will be admitted to the platform in the first place. DE07 primarily envisages other police services or border guard services on the platform - those organisations that have appropriate powers for such investigations (¶ 49). EX03 (¶ 69-73) and EX04 (¶ 51) see a conflict between the interests of police that want to collaborate on the topic of document authentication and data protection officers that want enforce the usage of established entities and processes such as SIRENE, Europol or Interpol.

On the legal side, it would require a “Errichtungsanordnung” (definition of the data collection which includes personal data) (EX08, ¶ 39). Legal compliance for the use of the (EX10, p. 2), political approval (PP01, ¶ 54) and clarification of the question which EU police authorities can access it in a legally binding way (PP01, item 72). In addition, it must be defined where it would be located (PP01, ¶ 72), before its installed in the adequate premises, once the technology is available (EX10, p. 2)

4.2 Assessment of Minor Success Factors

The minor success factors include IT Architecture, Marketing & Communication, Enterprise Culture, Pricing Structure, Legislation & Regulation. They are sorted in a descending order, according to Özcan et al. (2.4).

4.2.1 IT Architecture: Existing Platforms, Devices, Apps, and Connections. *Connecting databases may be a first step.* Systems are used to obtain reference images or query data. Some international systems are FIELDS with Quick Check Cards (DE04, ¶ 45, EX06, ¶ 40, EX08, ¶ 59), iFADO (DE06, ¶ 60, EX01, ¶ 15, EX06, ¶ 26, EX07, ¶ 23, DE03, ¶ 9) to which the UK has lost access due to the Brexit (DE04, ¶ 23) and PRADO (DE04, ¶ 23, EX01, ¶ 15). The “Schengen Information System” provides access to data (EX07, ¶ 20). Interpol runs I-24 (DE04, ¶ 23) and the SLTD, which provides information about “Stolen and Lost Travel Documents” (EX02, ¶ 68, EX07, ¶ 20). The “Secure Information Exchange Network Application” (SIENA) is used for international data exchange (PP01, ¶ 37).

This paragraph provides an incomplete overview over different national IT systems. Some of them are shared, especially within the DACH region (DE06, ¶ 56, DE09, item 15). Switzerland operates ARKILA (DE03, ¶ 9, DE09, ¶ 15) and “D232” (DE03, ¶ 9). Germany runs DOKIS (DE03, ¶ 9, DE09, ¶ 15), a proprietary system “Informationssystem Urkunde” (EX07, ¶ 23) the “Länderinformations- und Erkenntnisssystem” (EX08, ¶ 29) and a national search system (EX07, ¶ 20). In Austria, there is ARGUS (DE03, ¶ 9, DE09, ¶ 15) and the “Urkunden Überprüfungssystem” (DE06, ¶ 11). Anyone can access their online platform, but only the next higher document experts can add information (DE06, ¶ 56). In Addition, an eLearning Program with 40 hours of training is provided, where employees receive an entry in their education passport after successfully completing a course (DE06, ¶ 56). Turkey provides an online interface that converts personal data into identification numbers, or identification numbers into personal data. (DE02, ¶ 106). Ukrainian document experts support a domestic platform (DE08, ¶ 38) and the UK Home Office has a “work in progress” knowledge base for documents (DE04, ¶ 39) and the UK passport office as their own databases (DE04, ¶ 23). Lithuania provides a database to verify residence and settlement permits through phone (DE06, ¶ 44).

Although there are plenty of systems, “No one reference system consists of all 100% of documents. We're using three, maybe five.” (EX06, ¶ 105). There is no document specific collaboration platform within Zurich (DE05, ¶ 45). There is a “Visum Information System” but in general, there should be more systems for collaboration (DE05, ¶ 52-53).

The portable equipment varies between police forces of different countries.

Most police forces run work mobile phones (DE05, Pos.13, DE06, ¶ 10, DE07. Pos. 91, PP01, ¶ 60, PP03, ¶ 53, PP04, ¶ 9, DE09, ¶ 23, PP05, ¶ 63, EX09, ¶ 54, SC03, ¶ 63). Some work phones are operated as pool devices (EX07, ¶ 18, PP01, ¶ 22). There is a mix of iPhones (DE01, ¶ 49, DE03, ¶ 84, DE05, ¶ 77) and Android phones (DE04, ¶ 120, PP02, ¶ 83). Some have tablets or smartphones (DE08, ¶ 55) or iPads (DE01, ¶ 49) which are in some cases only found in a car (DE05, ¶ 77). Austria does not use tablets anymore (DE06, ¶ 126). Only approved applications can be installed on work devices, applications are stored in secure containers: One for police applications and the second one for public applications, such as rail or air connections (EX07, ¶ 16). A special case is the UK Border Force: “We have a company smartphone, but it doesn't have anything on it. Don't know why we have it, to be honest.” (PP02, ¶ 81). SC01 (¶ 13) mentions that not every police officer in Southern Europe has a computer or smartphone.

Torches are widely available (PP03, ¶ 53, PP04, ¶ 9, DE03, ¶ 82, DE07, ¶ 95) as personal equipment or within the car (DE06, ¶ 11), sometimes even with other light sources such as UV light (DE05, ¶ 77).

Magnifiers are available (PP03, ¶ 7, ¶ 53, PP04, ¶ 9, SC01, ¶ 13, PP04, ¶ 9) in car or personal equipment (DE05, ¶ 77, DE06, ¶ 11, ¶ 124, DE09, ¶ 23), but it is not a standard (DE09, ¶ 85). The magnifying glass on the smartphone is not bad (DE07, ¶ 95). Individual police officers have magnifiers such as the “Doculus Lumus”, which is considered the Rolls Royce among devices and would be too sophisticated for normal patrol officers (DE01, item 53, DE07, ¶ 95, SC03, ¶ 8). Sophisticated magnifiers are only in use near the border (EX07, ¶ 22). At customs, everyone has a hand-held tester with UV, anti-stokes, magnification, grazing light, UV light and, of course, torch. Certain cantonal police do not have such equipment (DE03, ¶ 13). Some police members carry a combination of verification device and smartphone as standard

equipment (PP05, ¶ 61) and others must buy own magnifiers (PP02, ¶ 87). Even the registry office has ID card readers but also light sources and magnifying glasses. (EX07, ¶ 65)

In Austria, the alien police officer has a laptop, the normal patrol officer does not. (DE09, ¶ 85). In Switzerland, everyone at the BAZG (PP03, ¶ 53) and all employees of the cantonal police Berne can communicate through Mail on a computer (DE07, ¶ 91). In Ukraine at least many (EX09, ¶ 54) have Laptops (DE08, ¶ 55, EX09, ¶ 54). Employees at airports have a computer which makes networking and communication easier – especially in combination with document verification devices and access to document information systems (DE06, ¶ 10). An advantage of computers are big screens or even multiple screens (EX07, ¶ 23) and that they have access to police-networks (EX07, ¶ 72) and other systems (PP01, ¶ 37). The UK Border Force can use a computer with a regular document scanner (PP02, ¶ 79) and a wired connection, but no Wi-Fi (PP02, ¶ 91).

Forensic equipment is mostly reserved for experts. At the airport, experts have everything within reach: The document reader taking UV pictures and infrared pictures, the document information system and time (DE06, ¶ 11). Similarly at the police station, they have document boxes and low-level microscopes. The high-end devices are then located in the document technology department (DE06, ¶ 127-128). Customs in Switzerland have microscopes available in some places and larger document examination equipment in others (PP03, ¶ 7). Stereomicroscopes and document examination devices from the company Projectina combine many different light sources (DE05, item 84) and some document scanners extract data from the MRZ and the chip automatically. In addition, it displays the Quick-Check-Cards from the FIELDS system (EX06, ¶ 46-47). Better equipment helps because pictures from (forensic) document readers can be sent to experts. They receive a white light image, a UV image, and an infrared image. This enables different conclusions to be drawn for remote consulting, compared to a blurred white light image from a smartphone (DE02, item 33). Ports in England do not use any document readers at first line (PP02, ¶ 7) and one would have to go to a special machine for a check, decreasing throughput (PP02, ¶ 10). First registration and foreigners' authorities in Germany were equipped with document readers (EX06, ¶ 65). The Service Center 03 offers some residents' registration offices a combination of an ID scanner with associated software. This can

be used to check documents in the common sizes ID1, ID2 and ID3. Birth certificates or similar can be checked via a photo or a good [high DPI] scan via office scanner (SC02, ¶ 22-23).

A standardized set of equipment would help. Although there are computers, smartphones, torches, magnifiers and forensic devices, there were mentions about desired or missing devices and functionality. As seen earlier, not all police officers have the tools for document checking (DE08, ¶ 11-16). Patrolmen do not have ultraviolet or infrared light (EX07, ¶ 23). For the Federal Police, a UV magnifying glass should be part of the vehicle equipment but also of the personnel equipment. In some countries, this is either vehicle equipment or even only precinct equipment (DE02, ¶ 100). Within Germany, standards on technical equipment for each of the three levels of document examination are still in development (EX08, ¶ 45). It would be beneficial for remote authentication, if a smartphone could be connected to a magnifier, to capture a picture and send it to the expert (DE05, ¶ 80) and to achieve that, the magnifying glass should correspond to the lens geometry of the smartphone for fewer reflections and optical interference (SC01, ¶ 18). In rare cases, “anything to check if it's a counterfeit, it's your own eyes.” (PP02, ¶ 79).

Police apps exist in different maturity levels. Germany introduced a “Polizei Messenger” (Police messenger) app that works like WhatsApp. It is used to exchange pictures (DE02, ¶ 33) There are further specialized apps for data extraction and search of people (EX07, ¶ 20, PP01, ¶ 60) and to extract and cross-compare document data and chip data (EX07, ¶ 20, PP01, ¶ 22). It is also possible to access existing databases like iFADO, PRADO or EDISON (PP01, ¶ 60). In the future, it will be possible to capture fingerprints through the camera (EX07, ¶ 21). The helpdesk app helped to capture multiple pictures of a case (like passport data page and visa stickers) for further processing through the team (EX07, ¶ 21, PP01, ¶ 22). A quick fix to address language barriers will be the “Formblatt” which translates common descriptions into the precise foreign language. The “Formblatt” is currently in development.

Austria also has an internal instant messaging service (DE06, ¶ 112, ¶ 117). ARGUS can be accessed through the smartphone (DE09, ¶ 85). The Federal Police “Bundespolizei” can reach document experts through a helpdesk app (PP05, ¶ 23). The

BAZG from Switzerland has no proprietary messenger but uses secure email between devices (DE03, ¶ 52).

“The Dutch are already pretty far along with smartphone technology. Then the French started, the Germans, the Austrians, etc. and everyone has such a different level with their technology. And they also use these phones for different things. They were not developed to exchange document information, but they were actually introduced to exchange other police information. And the document authenticity check is a side effect.” (SC01, ¶ 25)

Public apps and private devices are still in use. Public messenger apps such as WhatsApp were used in the past, before police messengers were introduced (DE02, ¶ 33) but the mobile device management of the police phones does not allow the installation of unapproved [public] apps anymore (SC01, ¶ 25). As a federal authority, you are not allowed to use public instant messenger services (DE08, ¶ 50). The German Document Helpdesk sometimes receives inquiries from private email addresses. If they are not known yet, they verify with local authorities if it is an official inquiry from a legit person before an answer to the private email address is provided (EX07, ¶ 25). There are at least five different Telegram groups connecting around 2000 police members. They are used for inquiries about documents, car license plates, drivers’ licenses (EX03, ¶ 7, EX04, ¶ 16) Viber is used for smaller local groups in Lithuania (EX03, ¶ 69-71). WhatsApp is in use in Greece (EX06, p. 105) and personal phones are used for video calls (EX09, ¶ 59).

Networks are not always available or connected. Bad signal at airports can render apps unusable (PP02, ¶ 93) and especially near the border, the radio network can become a problem (PP03, ¶ 53). All kinds of authorities are networked with each other but there are still many authorities that are not joint to the one common network (DE02, ¶ 59).

4.2.2 Marketing & Communication. Marketing and communication of the platform must address all different perspectives, from the patrol police to document experts to executives: people checking the documents want to make sure it’s a genuine document and don’t mind queues. Executives look at efficiency and are happy if throughput can be increased thanks to a platform (PP02, ¶ 58). Whenever a local

helpdesk from the JETs project is set up, it must be ensured that all patrol officers know that the helpdesk exists for it to be used (EX07, item 43). The usage of document authentication services depends on the communication. People must know that there is such a service and what it is good for. The document helpdesks live from their awareness and must introduce themselves, advertise their services and must let people know that they are there for them (SC03, ¶ 29). There should be a very strong lead-team promoting the project. Without proper promotion, the project will not be used. Patrol must see their benefits to get an intrinsic motivation to use the new solution. This spreads the word and attracts more users. Without clear benefit, users must but will not use the platform and the organisation just pays (EX01, ¶ 63).

4.2.3 Enterprise Culture: Motivation, Readiness, Willingness. *The personal mindset towards document authentication varies.* On a spectrum of document experts, there are two extremes: In the most positive case, there are people who have been confronted with the topic, have fun with it, have familiarised themselves with it professionally and participate with joy and expertise. In the most negative case, they are people who have chosen the niche to be promoted more quickly thanks to the dominant knowledge (DE02, ¶ 41).

Not all employees have the same motivation to check identity documents in depth (DE05, item 9). The way ID cards are checked depends on the level of training and interest of the police officer (PP04, ¶ 9). Even if all the vehicles were equipped with magnifying glasses, it is up to the employee to use it (DE09, ¶ 23). Colleagues need a checking technique and must be sensitive to the fact that they can also be shown false documents. However, the colleagues must also remember that fact when they check a person and inspect a document. (PP01, item 9). No police member is going to wait up to ten minutes to receive an assessment of a document expert if they do not have an initial doubt about the documents' authenticity (PP01, ¶ 20). Document experts often provide unpaid, telephone support in private time and at home. They consider this to be more of a collegial service (DE06, ¶ 10, EX03, ¶ 13).

There will always be innovators, early adopters, the majority, and laggards². There will be both, those who are more inclined towards innovations and want to implement something new, and those who are sceptical. (PP04, ¶ 63) Some look

² According to Diffusion of Innovations, (Rogers, 2003, p. 11)

forward to new apps and technical aids, others are not well versed in technology will have difficulty using the platform (PP03, ¶ 73). As today becomes more and more digital, the digital readiness of the individual employees increases (DE07, ¶ 107).

The average age at the frontline continues to fall. Fresh colleagues have grown up with digital technology, are digitally affine, and will therefore use the technology after they have been trained (PP05, ¶ 65). The technology must be accompanied by professionals so that no wrong conclusions are drawn (DE02, ¶ 106). Digital solutions are generally easier for the younger generation (EX08, ¶ 76) who are more open, trusting and interested towards new things (DE02, ¶ 106, DE03, ¶ 90, DE05, ¶ 92, DE06, ¶ 133, PP02, ¶ 95, EX06, ¶ 130). Now, they work with old databases and equipment (EX06, ¶ 130). It is different for the older generation (EX08, ¶ 76, DE05, ¶ 92) because they may be reluctant to any sort of technology (PP02, ¶ 95) and are cautious due to their experience from previous activities and systems (DE06, ¶ 133). Even people above 50 are keen to use it, although digital experience varies (EX08, ¶ 76). In addition, the higher the age, the more difficult becomes to deal with new systems. (SC03, ¶ 65). The older generation would also be less affected (DE05, ¶ 92).

The digital readiness is increasing. DE04 estimates that Europe is ready, mainly from a technological point of view. (¶ 112) but EX08 adds that digital dexterity differs from for example Germany and western Balkans (¶ 76). Estonia is generally considered as a well-developed country and people are happy to use digital tools that ease their work in the field (EX01, ¶ 57). Patrol police in Ukraine is already working with on-line databases but do not have the capability to exchange picture video, direct chat, or video calls (EX09, ¶ 59).

Digital readiness depends on the purpose of the platform (general purpose, investigation, legal status, migration) and on the field of expertise. It varies from unit to unit (EX02, ¶ 82). Considering the spread of private chats for document checking, EX04 thinks that the platform would certainly be a success (EX04, ¶ 142).

While FRONTEX has a network of more than 100 document experts, trained in their field of document authentication, they do not have a lot of experience about remote document authentication but are keen to learn (EX10, p. 3). In contrast to this statement, EX05 (¶ 148) elaborates that document experts needed the document in

their hand five to ten years ago, but nowadays accept new digital solutions to evaluate documents and even chips from a distance.

SC01 (¶ 16-17) refers to an internal study which took place some years back. They investigated tools in use, components for the future and which database queries from the past. It was surprising how diverse the European police operate and how different apps provide various functions. Smartphone-based solutions do enjoy high acceptance because people transfer processes and use cases from other areas of their life into work (SC02, ¶ 85).

The majority is willing to collaborate through a platform. Greek document expert would be excited to have and use a platform as soon as possible (EX03, ¶ 93). Italy is also included, if data security (EX04, ¶ 14-15) and authorization of their administration (EX04, ¶ 143-149) is guaranteed. Their staff and administration would be honoured and proud to work in a platform (EX04, ¶ 111). The city of Amsterdam already collaborates with parties in and outside Netherlands, but through other means than a platform (EX05, ¶ 150-152). EX06 from Lithuania answered that they “definitely” and “of course” would collaborate with other police through the platform (¶ 133-134). PP01 draws from personal experience and personal networks from Italy and Spain and is certain that such a system would be used (¶ 68). EX01 thinks that the Estonian police and other authorities will be interested in the collaboration. (EX01, ¶ 49) and FRONTEX already collaborates with European police through the JET project³ (EX10, p. 3).

The human factor and the working-environment factor are influencing the willingness to collaborate through a platform (SC01, ¶ 16-17). Its acceptance could be boosted, if it was introduced as an add-on to the existing German “Urkundenapp” (Documents app), including document experts and multipliers (EX08, ¶ 33). The older generation may be reluctant to provide help through a platform (DE06, ¶ 133).

DE01 thinks that the platform is rarely used [in the Zurich area] because two ID card verification offices in the canton of Zurich offer ID card verification services from 0600 to 2200 (DE01, ¶ 65).

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1qkRI4fDYiQ>

4.2.4 Pricing Structure: Funds, Transactions, Licensing. *Somehow, somebody, must pay the bill.* The development of the platform can be funded through different approaches. There are, apart from others, possibilities to pay a lump sum for development or finance the platform through its transaction costs (EX07, ¶ 25). A cost benefit analysis shall be carried out before the payment model is decided (EX10, p. 2).

It is very difficult to get money from a fund from a ministry of the interior (DE02, ¶ 91). With every fake identity document that is taken out of circulation, an average loss of up to 60,000 € is saved. Decisive bodies understand this in such a diffuse way that it is not seen as a concrete added value. Added value needs to be understood to receive funds from the ministry of the interior. Money would be saved in the social sector by investing it in the interior (DE02, ¶ 80-81).

The organisations that can save training time or manpower are the institutions most interested in funding this. (DE01, ¶ 37, EX01, ¶ 51). The participating countries could pay a lump sum to finance the project (DE03, ¶ 74). The first hurdle in Switzerland would be the assignment of the leading party, for example some cantonal police or the BAZG. Many projects start with a motivated party, and later, when the questions about the operator or about paying the bills, projects are abandoned (DE03, ¶ 76). DE03 considers the issues around payments to be the biggest showstoppers (¶ 92).

Frontex could develop it (EX08, ¶ 27): JETs is funded by FRONTEX (DE03, ¶ 50), who were funded from the EU Internal Security Fund, through an own project and European partners (DE06, ¶ 101, EX07, ¶ 25) because Frontex is the main agency for external borders and could propose projects to EU by themselves (EX06, ¶ 109) but it is presumptuous to say that the platform will be in Frontex' area responsibility (DE06, ¶ 101). The country should pay for it through a common organisation such as Europol or Interpol (EX03, ¶ 97). With the Interpol Funding model, Members contribute into the pot which is used to fund the development and running costs of the platform. Members get access in return (DE04, ¶ 88). The membership-fee could be based on the country's GDP (DE04, ¶ 92). Similarly, EX03 (¶ 73) recommends financing the platform through a basic fee as an ICAO member state.

An EU fund (EX01, ¶ 51, EX04, ¶ 113, SC03, ¶ 59) for Europe's internal security (DE05, ¶ 55, EX08, ¶ 27) could finance the platform. The downside of EU projects is

the runtime of seven years with uncertainty about the continuation and future funding (SC03, ¶ 59).

Countries had to finance such activities by themselves until now (DE06, ¶ 101). If the project would start on a national level in Switzerland, the parties must determine if the costs are covered by the federal government or the cantons. (DE03, ¶ 76). To prevent fraud, private and public sectors should work and invest together (EX05, ¶ 86) even if a solution from the private sector costs more but may on the other hand be ready sooner (SC03, ¶ 59).

The introduction of transaction costs was viewed controversially, rather negatively. The German federal police and the Swiss cantonal agencies cooperate with partners without mutually invoicing each other for services (DE07, item 85, EX07, item 86)

“Wenn wir die Länder unterstützen, die Bundesländer, dann stellen wir auch was in Rechnung. Wenn wir andere Bundesbehörden unterstützen, dann wird nichts in Rechnung gestellt, weil der Bund sich gegenseitig nicht in die Tasche greift.” (If we support federal states, then we charge something. If we support other federal authorities, then we don't charge anything, because the federal governments do not reach into each other's pockets.) (EX08, ¶ 27)

Some document experts provide their services for their colleagues even after working hours. They consider their efforts paid through their salary, and they do not feel the need for extra compensation per transaction (DE06, ¶ 101, DE07, ¶ 87, DE08, ¶ 45, EX09, ¶ 44).

There will be asymmetries in demand for support and supply of expert knowledge. One example was given by EX02: “The small Pacific Island Vanuatu probably wants to know all European passports, while Europeans hardly ever see a Vanuatu passport in Europe”. This would lead to some countries paying the maximum price because they have the highest demand for consultation (¶ 71) or run out of money the quickest, which would defeat the purpose (EX02, ¶ 75). On the other hand, the German federal police would not be able to sustain an international helpdesk by themselves (EX07, ¶ 26). Three participants think that there is no need for transaction costs and they would deter the platforms use (DE02, ¶ 88, DE04, ¶ 88, EX08, ¶ 27).

Police would quickly question the utility of the platform if a transaction would be billed, for example with 10 CHF (DE04, ¶ 91-92). Police funding is not the same across different countries hence it may not be applicable (SC03, ¶ 59). While transaction costs can be added to transactions at for example registry offices, who have fixed prices for the issuance of a passport, transaction costs are not always applicable in police work (DE02, ¶ 88). In an EU / Schengen project, the service must be offered regardless of the costs (DE05, ¶ 61) but pricing must be considered in the budgeting process, although invoices may only be sent and paid fictitious (DE02, ¶ 86).

Transaction costs would be helpful because one organisation would only have to pay per use, regardless of the costs in the background (EX05, ¶ 101). Through transaction costs (or a flat-rate standby fee), document experts can be motivated to work after business hours, although a document expert cannot influence how many inquiries arrive per day (DE06, ¶ 106-109). Police officers download images from databases and then share it in groups, sometimes with undesired participants. The introduction of a transaction cost could be a good tool to reduce the unwanted spread of information (EX04, ¶ 61). Transaction costs with dynamic pricing would not work for police but could be used for a lower spec service offered to private companies requesting help from document experts.

“They could use dynamic pricing for inquiries from a Bank: On a quiet time on Wednesday afternoon, 15:00, charging 4€, but price could go up to 23€ at 10:00 on a Monday when more checks are pending.” (DE04, ¶ 101-102).

The commercially run service center SC02 may work with transaction fees to cover their costs, given there are some details about estimated transaction volumes and fees (¶ 67). It would be possible to work with contingents to avoid individual invoices (¶ 69)

A last option would be working with traditional licenses.

If a police organisation decides to develop a platform themselves, they can decide if they want to commission the application just for themselves, pass it on to other countries free of charge or provide it through commercial licences (EX08, ¶ 23). Participants agrees that, however costs are levied, it should be the organisation, state

or country paying for it, and not the individual police officer submitting a request for support (EX03, ¶ 97, EX09, ¶ 42, DE05, ¶ 57, DE08, ¶ 43).

4.2.5 Legislation & Regulation: Data Protection, General Legal Framework, Accountability and Liability, Censorship. *Different data protection laws and regulations are considered the biggest showstopper for a platform.* The chances for an international platform are low, given the different, country specific regulation and legislations, mainly because of the sensitive information of personal data (EX01, ¶ 55, EX04, ¶ 116, EX06, ¶ 120-122, SC01, ¶ 19). EX01 thinks that there is a chance (EX01, ¶ 52-53). From the EU perspective, the most important regulations are the general data protection regulation from the EU, then the law enforcement directive where police can share more, and then the intelligence services with even more sharing but a very limited scope (EX02, ¶ 77-80). The restrictions to share data depends on the purpose how the data will be used (EX02, ¶ 84, EX06, ¶ 112). While technological security can be achieved, aggregated information from identity, vehicle registration and other sources are difficult to handle. SC02 (¶ 59 -61) agrees that the huge amount of personal data and data protection would be a challenge, although cybersecurity may offer lean solutions such as transaction-based case-encryption. The location of the data which are collected and processed, is also important (PP01, ¶ 48). PP04 (¶ 39) considers data protection as a main thread for the feasibility of an international collaboration platform but adds that apart from that, there would be only upsides for front and patrol police work, although there may be financial impacts because the platform would require infrastructure and personnel in the background. DE07 (¶ 63), EX03 (¶ 119) and EX04 (¶ 49) consider data protection laws and data regulations a main reason for why such a platform would never be established or would at least struggle with its implementation. At least in Netherlands, there are different identity authentication levels that may enable a collaboration: Under GDPR, a police officer can request the drivers' license during a check and query the person through the database to see if there are any open cases. If there are matches, the law enforcement directive applies different rules and enables deeper identity authentication. (EX02, ¶ 86)

“An investigator and as a law enforcement person, I want to, of course, have all the data. As a private person, I want to make sure that my data is

properly protected and that it's not out there for anyone. So, it's, it's a difficult balance.” (EX02, ¶ 55)

Some thoughts on how to protect personal data. For their non-binding legal helpdesk consultations, the German federal data protection officer established a “Errichtungsanordnung”⁴: The policy specifies that all personal data must be permanently, non-recoverably deleted at the end of every day (EX07, ¶ 29). Police generally tries to operate self-sufficient and exclude private companies from their data operations, which is good for data protection (EX07, ¶ 84). platform would support data protection through end user agreements to which participating members would have to comply with (DE04, ¶ 30). The data protection topic must be investigated thoroughly and there must be “watertight legal guarantees” about access and use of the information (DE04, ¶ 45). Apart from data protection laws, police organisations may have individual IT security policies, which cover police service media (PP01, ¶ 22). The BAZG avoids data protection violation by using only internal email systems between their devices instead of any public applications (DE03, ¶ 52) because data protection laws prohibit the use of public applications to send personal data (DE03, ¶ 50). Poland is very strict (DE09, ¶ 76) and only allows personal data queries with justification of which officer asked and for what reason (EX03, ¶ 65), but they could nevertheless provide feedback about an inquiry on the base of a picture of an ID card. Greece has similar data protection mechanisms, but they are less strict (EX03, ¶ 67). FADO Regulation “(EU) 2020/493” covers police cooperation and leaves room that Frontex could offer FADO services to police officers (EX10, p. 2). Ukraine considers it difficult to answer questions about the legal feasibility of such a platform, “given the situation in the country [Ukraine]” (EX09, ¶ 49).

Data protection laws exist to protect people. EX03 (¶ 52) points out that it is not always clear who operates certain databases that are queried. This can be problematic for a person with asylum status because the data provider, for example an administration of their country of origin, may gather details about time and location of the query, which may have negative consequences for the person. DE04 (¶ 29) explains that the UK would only exchange personal information with countries where the death penalty still applies under the condition that there is a legal assurance that such

⁴ A definition of the data collection which includes personal data.

consequences will not be applied. In Germany (DE02, ¶ 95), the international police department would inform an officer, that a certain request could lead to a death sentence, and that the request therefore won't be carried out.

There will be a lot of paperwork. It needs international contracts to connect countries outside Schengen (DE05, ¶ 43) and some doubt that everybody can agree on the privacy laws worldwide (EX05, ¶ 111-113). Europol and Frontex do have additional agreements with third countries (EX07, ¶ 80). For international collaboration, the clear distinction between police assistance and legal aid must be defined before additional contracts are established. While Europe can collaborate, it will become much more difficult when involving western Balkans or Africa (EX08, ¶ 66). Austria works for years towards a data exchange with Bulgaria, even just for basic information such as the previous issuance of a drivers' license, but struggles with national policies within Europe (DE09, ¶ 32). Other International, platform-based collaboration must be legally regulated (DE05, ¶ 43, DE07, ¶ 65) and the sweet spot between national and international rules for collaboration must be found (SC03, ¶ 61). Legal requirements should not be an issue, if the police departments see a necessity and a benefit (DE05, ¶ 67). If starting within the Schengen area, Schengen helps to foster data exchange between participating countries (DE05, ¶ 43, EX05, ¶ 109-115). The United Kingdom has lost access to several important databases due to Brexit (PP02, ¶ 32)

Data exchange examples from practice. It will depend on the definition of the collaboration. Swiss cantonal police can already selectively query data from other cantons, but it is not possible to systematically provide data to other cantons. It requires contracts which are continuously adapted (DE07, ¶ 65). Although it may be possible to submit police data or even personal data to private companies if it is necessary for the settlement of a case as per federal police law, it is practically impossible, because the transfer of such data is never mandatory (EX07, ¶ 56).

International collaboration requires a single point of cont(r)act. A Swiss cantonal document expert was not allowed to participate in the JETs project because current contracts between Switzerland and EU require a single point of contact for international police inquiries. For Switzerland, this is FEDPOL, hence the cantonal

document expert was not allowed to participate (DE07, ¶ 71). A FEDPOL employee on the other hand would be eligible to participate (DE07, ¶ 72-75).

Police officer of the first control level cannot call anyone in a foreign country for assistance. There are defined, hierarchical channel with defined rights. The defined path is State Office of Criminal Investigation, Federal Police, Interpol, and on the other side in reverse order. (PP01, ¶ 37)

The important difference between “Polizeiliche Amtshilfe” (police assistance) and “Rechtshilfe” (legal aid). Germany distinguishes between “Polizeiliche Amtshilfe” (Police assistance) und “Rechtshilfe” (Legal aid). Whereas the current helpdesks only inspect document properties and offer *consulting* within police assistance, they avoid processing personal data and do not issue a formal forensic expert report, to stay out of the legal aid area. Because they consult on an optional base, before an official investigation was triggered, the requesting party remains in charge and responsibility (EX07, ¶ 28, SC01 Pos. 29). This is also in the interest of patrol police (PP05, ¶ 57). In contrast to the German service centers, the “Gemeinsame Zentren” (Joint Centers between two countries) can also query personal data. (SC03, ¶ 39). Spanish centers even draw up expert reports from their consultation (EX07, ¶ 44).

Binding and accountability of remote support. A document expert (or rather his organisation) can be held accountable for consequences of their decision, such as a missed flight (SC01, ¶ 54-56) but it has yet to be defined how binding the recommendations from the remote consulting are. SC01 considers the police officer that requests support in charge, as the service center does not have physical access to the document to come to a final assessment. A similar distinction between consulting and final assessment takes place in Bern (DE07, ¶ 9). The commercial document consulting company provides an evaluation or confirms or denies anomalies through remote services. They also operate on the consulting level without obligations, because physical access would be required to generate a final report (SC02, ¶ 41). Their document experts cannot be held accountable for their decisions (¶ 76-77).

Legal and formal requirements. The (Swiss) law differentiates between fake detection and authenticity check. While it is simple to classify fakes (whereof 80% are clumsy), an authenticity check requires total certainty that a document is genuine

(DE05, ¶ 15). In Germany, the public prosecutor's office may ask for a written expert opinion. (DE02, ¶ 25) because police cannot present any communication from any platform or messenger to a judge (¶ 35). On the other hand, if the platform follows defined steps and is considered approved, that data could be used, too (¶ 38-39), if they follow the required norms like ISO/IEC17020, ISO/IEC17025 (¶ 50). In one case, a remote assessment from a Greek police officer was accepted by the public prosecutor's office during a case (EX03, ¶ 131). They usually follow the tree level system [first line officer, second line with advanced training and third line being document experts] where only the highest level of document experts is eligible to create expert reports which can be used in criminal proceedings (EX07, ¶ 7). In United Kingdom, any police officer can produce a witness statement for court (DE04, ¶ 19) although less experienced officers prefer to get a statement from home office document experts. Document experts in Netherlands do have a (professional) certificate and create reports that can be used in court (EX05, ¶ 25).

Partial censorship of personal data would be a possible compromise. DE02 (¶ 95) elaborates that personal data is not required for questions around issuing modalities such as known errors within the ICAO MRZ area, or different fonts. DE06 (¶ 122) considers anonymisation a good approach. Document experts inspect the carrier and not the person. If a document was a car, he'd inspect if the car has any defects, and not the driver himself. DE08 (¶ 52) and EX09 (¶ 51) agree by simply answering "yes" to the question if censoring would help tackling data protection issues. The Greek identity document has few security elements and is basically a piece of paper. EX03 can detect most fakes, even drivers' licenses and passports and just from a picture without any personal details. (EX03, ¶ 109-111). It is possible to assess document authenticity without sharing all personal details or images required to determine one's identity (EX01, ¶ 55).

DE05 (¶ 73) doubts that the anonymization of identity documents would be a purposeful solution, as it would obscure relevant areas. Nevertheless, it'd be "besser als nichts" (better than nothing). EX04 (¶ 127-134) mentions that censoring of data would make it impossible to detect cases where photographs of the rightful owner were exchanged. However, EX05 (¶ 118-131) and EX06 (¶ 124-125) agree that for the comparison of printing technologies, it would be sufficient to receive fragments of the

photograph, because in that case, it is not a goal to detect lookalikes but to authenticate the document.

Censoring of personal data would make authenticity checks difficult. The quality of an assessment would depend on the image resolution. Document examination consists of different factors (DE01, ¶ 47). PP04 (¶ 53) argues that the comparison of personal data would be of biggest value of international collaboration. Without personal data, it would not be possible to query data bases and the check would be reduced to security elements. To verify if a certain person is eligible to drive, an inquiry without personal data does not make sense (DE02, ¶ 95).

4.3 Use Cases for Platform-Based Collaboration

Three major codes emerge from the coded data, being “potential use cases”, “value proposition” and “current problems”. Within the qualitative data, I identified 189 use-case relevant segments through inductive coding. From these segments, non-thesis-relevant and non-platform-based statements were excluded. The remaining passages were consolidated into six use-cases. I sorted the use cases by number of coded segments and assigned relevant value propositions and problems to it to describe holistic use cases, which I individually describe using the general structure of Intro, what, why, how, and why a platform is suitable.

Table 1: Overview of Use Cases for Platform-Based Collaboration

Title (Number of Coded Segments)	Summary of the use-case
Data Verification (46)	An identity document from country A is shown in country B. Someone from country B checks with country A, based on data and possibly the photo, whether the identity document was issued in the constellation.
Guided Assistance (43)	A person presents an ‘uncommon’ identity document to patrol police. Patrol police uses remote expert for a first assessment of the document through the exchange of pictures and voice instructions.
Collaborative Knowledge base (24)	Experts around the world maintain similar knowledgebases for authentic documents

	and series of forgeries, which could be combined into one platform for patrol police and document experts.
Expert Exchange (23)	An expert-to-expert platform would support experts in determining document authenticity on the base of case-specific, more sophisticated images obtained from forensic equipment.
Rights, Permits and Visa Consulting (7)	Different areas require a lot of specific knowledge which can be overwhelming for a patrol police unit, for example heavy goods traffic regulations, visa codes, immigration requirements. A consulting platform would help.
Imposter Detection (1)	Patrol police could request remote support of experts in imposter detections, which would support patrol police in comparing images from identity document with the person undergoing police checks.

4.3.1 Case “Data Verification”

Data verification exists on an inter-organisation or even national basis (DE01, ¶ 55, DE02, ¶ 28, DE09, ¶ 40). For cars, there is a European information system called EUCARIS, but for identities, there is no broad system yet (DE09, ¶ 53). In such a system, police can query if one has for example a driving license or certain travel documents. Such a system would be used if there are indication that a presented document was obtained by fraud (DE03, ¶ 28, DE08, ¶ 24) or something is wrong (DE03, ¶ 58).

Figure 8 Use Case "Data Verification" (Own Illustration)

A subset of name, dates, document numbers and list are important. A police member would query if a person with the given combination of document number, name, date of birth and nationality exists (DE01, ¶ 55, DE03, ¶ 28, EX07, ¶ 14, PP04, ¶ 27, EX02, ¶ 58, PP03, ¶ 51, PP04, ¶ 11, PP04, ¶ 17). Ideally, a picture of the person would be returned for comparison against the presented document or matched automatically (DE01, ¶ 55, DE03, ¶ 28, EX02, ¶ 58). The case can extend to residence permits and authorisations from abroad because it can be unclear what rights come with a certain permit (DE05, ¶ 51). In situations where a person arrives at a road traffic control without carrying their driving licence, the police officer wants to know whether a driver's licence was issued in the country of origin (DE09, ¶ 19). A police officer may also want to query if ID with a given number is wanted or was reported stolen (SC01, ¶ 9).

The main reason for a query is confirmation and trust. The direct data query would confirm issuance modalities (DE02, ¶ 28, DE05, ¶ 29, DE09, ¶ 9, EX06, ¶ 127, PP04, ¶ 58-59), could reassure the officer if a forgery is not recognised immediately (DE09, ¶ 21, EX03, ¶ 13) and would be based on reliable data (EX02, ¶ 58). Databases also provide information about existence, issuance, or if IDs were stolen (PP04, ¶ 11). The picture is beneficial for facial comparison because data can be stolen and used with another picture (DE03, ¶ 28, DE05, ¶ 29). A Refugee obtaining a status in country A can travel to country B within the Schengen area and is never seen in country A again. Country B needs to be able to query the status from country A (EX01, ¶ 17). There are even bidirectional use-cases, where for example an intoxicated person from country A would lose its driver's license in country B and the revocation should be reported back to the original country (EX02, ¶ 86).

There are ideas about how it would work. A police officer in Germany could query the Polish driving license system with the data on the driver's license (male, name, document number) and the system would return a female person for the same document number, indicating that the details provided are wrong (DE02, ¶ 28, ¶ 55) or a French system does return details about an issued document when a document number is entered (SC03, ¶ 15). Currently, the Federal Police in Germany proxies similar request for local colleagues because they have the connections (DE02, ¶ 28). DE04 (¶ 59) would expand queries to national control rooms and the Interpol bureau. If police members from country A are not allowed to query data from country B, it may be enough to simply return a 'true or false' statement without providing any personal data or pictures of the holder. Although the information's usefulness depends on the extent it can be used during an investigation (SC03, ¶ 39).

A platform increases efficiency, establishes contacts and enables patrol police. One reason to do that through a platform would be a decrease in process time or an increase in efficiency (DE05, ¶ 51, DE09, ¶ 19, ¶ 29, SC01, ¶ 9) because national authorities who are not familiar with certain identity documents can be skipped to directly inquire with authorities of the concerning country (DE04, ¶ 80). The process still requires a lot of manpower, and the system would bridge training, experience, or expertise gaps (SC01, ¶ 9). There is no access to national databases of other EU countries (DE09, ¶ 29, ¶ 32, ¶ 91) and it could be combined with other databases such

as the Schengen Information System and Interpol databases for lost and stolen documents (EX07, ¶ 20).

4.3.2 Case “Guided Assistance”

Remote assistance relies on personal contacts established through foreign assignments. Automated matchmaking would be beneficial (DE06, ¶ 5). Now, remote support is rather self-service with a database instead of an interactive scenario. Support at the click of a button would be helpful (DE06, ¶ 69). Whenever a police officer cannot confiscate the document, a remote consultation could take place (DE07, ¶ 15).

Figure 9 Use Case "Guided Assistance" (Own Illustration)

Document specific knowhow can be delivered to the place of action. Remote experts can help officers determining if a questioned ID is a forgery or not (DE05, ¶ 13) or just help overcoming uncertainty through a first assessment. (EX07, ¶ 13). Experts can provide guidance about how to inspect specific elements, how they

behave, presence of micro text, design elements, printing techniques of IDs and how pictures should be integrated (DE02, ¶ 69, DE03, ¶ 43-44, DE05, ¶ 13, DE06, ¶ 11, DE06, ¶ 17) which is appreciated by the police officer (PP04, ¶ 17). Document experts have access to reference databases and descriptions (DE06, ¶ 11) and can provide reference images for A/B testing of, for example, a laser personalization and a toner personalization (DE07, ¶ 104-105, SC01, ¶ 62). They can assess the pictures they receive (EX07, ¶ 13) or provide feedback about the existence of a questioned document (PP05, ¶ 13). DE07 (¶ 103) adds that a remote support requires a basic training of the police officer because it could not be used for ad-hoc training in for example printing techniques. Nevertheless, general feedback about ID series would be supportive.

Uncertainty, doubt and lack of training can be overcome. Police officers may be unfamiliar with a certain document (DE03, ¶ 43-44, EX07, ¶ 13, PP01, ¶ 12) or doubt the authenticity of an ID (DE06, ¶ 112, DE07, ¶ 104-105, EX07, ¶ 13) or lack the training and technical knowledge to verify a documents authenticity (DE05, ¶ 13, EX07, ¶ 13) and it is extremely difficult to support verbally (PP01, ¶ 12).

The value lies in real-time communication and media exchange. The platform should generally connect police officer and helpdesk online (EX07, ¶ 13) or provide a helpdesk to reach the police officer directly (DE03, ¶ 86). Once connected, the helpdesk can guide the police officer through phone or voice and sequential questions and answers (DE02, ¶ 69, DE05, ¶ 13, DE07, ¶ 15, DE07, ¶ 37, EX05, ¶ 144, PP05, ¶ 13) and request certain images (DE03, ¶ 86, EX07, ¶ 22). During the process, the parties can exchange pictures from the ID or hotspots to inspect (DE03, ¶ 86, DE05, ¶ 13, DE07, ¶ 37, PP04, ¶ 25, PP05, ¶ 13, SC02, ¶ 25). Police officers can put a magnifying glass on the document and take a photo, which is then sent to the document expert (DE06, ¶ 19, ¶ 112, EX07, ¶ 22). Doculus Lumus has special versions where the mobile phone can be connected so that the colleagues can take enlarged pictures and send it to the helpdesk (EX07, ¶ 22). In a more sophisticated version of such support, document expert could connect to the police officers' phone which is on the magnifying glass to obtain real time insights while providing instructions about how to move the phone through voice commands (DE06, ¶ 22-23). It must be considered that photos generally provide higher image quality than (live) videos (DE07, item 95). The case is not limited to communication between police officers on mobile devices

and document experts on desktops – police officers could also submit high resolution scans from regular office scanners or even document readers (SC02, ¶ 25).

The platform speeds up processes and transfers work to the right place. The police officer can focus on the main task (DE06, ¶ 89-93) and with a quick response time of three to five minutes (DE06, ¶ 112, EX07, ¶ 13). There would be no need to clumsily find details about a document's security features in a big database (DE06, ¶ 89-93) because the right expert could be reached easily (DE06, ¶ 89-93) as information such as the phone number of the police officer seeking help can automatically be transmitted (EX07, ¶ 22). A platform would connect the patrol officer with experts of second and third competence level, making everyone an expert by establishing an online connection quickly (EX07, ¶ 14, SC03, ¶ 33). This helps because helpdesks provide an assessment, a building block from their perspective (SC03, ¶ 15). The document experts can work in their environment with the right periphery (EX07, item 23). Although a mobile phone offers less possibilities than document readers, it would bring a solution to the street where there is nothing now (EX05, ¶ 146). Even international support can be foreseen if the platform bridges the language barriers (DE06, ¶ 99). Finally, a police officer obtains certainty to move a person from a traffic check to a police station for further investigation, when an ID document fails a basic authenticity assessment (DE06, ¶ 17).

“Ein Bild sagt mehr als 1000 Worte und dann kann ich vielleicht mit einem Bild noch erklären: So, und da musst du hier vergrößern, dann musst du da mal schauen und das muss so aussehen und das muss die Funktion haben und dieses Merkmal muss die Funktion haben.” (A picture says more than a thousand words and then maybe I can explain with a picture: So, and you have to enlarge here, then you have to look there and that has to look like this and that has to have the function and this feature has to have the function.) (PP01, ¶ 41)

4.3.3 Case “Collaborative Knowledge Base”

For that case, every country would provide experts describing the local documents and users which consume existing descriptions (DE06, ¶ 68). The document experts (or criminal investigation department) would in that case be less interested in the results of an independent document issued by another country, but rather about general details in issuing modalities for future references of that document type (DE02, ¶ 28). Compared to “Guided Assistance” case, this is not interactive but rather a self-service database where I can look up (DE06, item 69).

Figure 10 Use Case "Collaborative Knowledge Base" (Own Illustration)

The knowledge base would cover descriptions about authentic documents, anomalies, and forgeries. In general, the platform should contain details about key security features with illustrated examples such as high-quality digital imagery, machine-readable zone, background prints and general design overviews (DE04, ¶ 61-

63). Countries could still reserve the right to covert some examination features (DE04, ¶ 63). Details of interest would be country-specific issuance practices which differ from the ICAO standard (DE02, ¶ 28). The knowledge base could also include non-forgery related issuance anomalies such as slightly different printing details because a new printer was installed at the issuing authority (PP03, ¶ 27). The platform could act as a catalogue of possible falsified documents (EX01, ¶ 15, EX09, ¶ 23). The experts would share anomalies, inviting others to share related experiences (DE04, ¶ 59, PP01, ¶ 46, PP02, ¶ 63, PP03, ¶ 27) which would lead to the identification of document parts which are forged less careful (PP02, ¶ 63) or identify series created by the same forgers to provide insights about their modus operandi (PP01, ¶ 46, PP02, ¶ 28, PP03, ¶ 27). The platform could expand the Frontex case of sharing Quick-Check-Cards. (EX06, ¶ 69-71)

The platform primarily supports self-aid and sharing of information. This platform can be used for knowledge sharing (EX01, ¶ 35, EX04, ¶ 81) and for training of the participants (EX01, ¶ 35, EX04, ¶ 83) and automated creation of alerts (EX04, ¶ 83). Information exchange is valuable to avoid false positives (where a well issued document with anomalies is classified as forgery) (PP03, ¶ 27). The different databases of Switzerland, Germany, Austria are already positioned so that a police officer can help himself (DE09, ¶ 67). But municipalities would benefit from access to documents and security elements as well (EX01, ¶ 35).

Participants exchange through give and take of information. The platform should be a collaborative workspace (DE04, ¶ 59) where each country provides details about their national documents (DE06, ¶ 63). Content can be moderated through different roles, such as police officers as ‘viewers and commentors’, and forensic departments as ‘editors’. Additional document details may be revealed through extra qualifications (DE06, ¶ 56). Some national systems already exchange information (DE06, ¶ 76), so a platform could act as a hub, connecting remaining systems (EX06, ¶ 105-106) or leveraging existing contacts and connections between experts (DE02, ¶ 28). Frontex’ system already bundles findings of their teams and provides them back to the participants (PP01, ¶ 26).

A platform supports efficiency and effectiveness. The collaboration through a platform would decrease detection time of forgery series (PP01, ¶ 46) and increase actuality of individual databases (PP04, ¶ 51).

“Man kann ja nicht alle Dokumente, die weltweit auf dem Markt sind, die ausgegeben werden, die kann man nicht alle kennen. Und ich glaube schon, dass eine solche Plattform (...) auch genutzt werden würde.” (You can't know all the documents that are on the market worldwide, that are issued, you can't know them all. And I do believe that such a platform (...) would also be used.) (PP01, ¶ 68)

4.3.4 Case “Expert Exchange”

This case combines “Guided Assistance” and “Collaborative knowledge base”, but with the difference of simply connecting experts with experts instead of police officers. While the interactions have the same character, the content would differ.

Document experts could request second opinions from other experts through the exchange of sophisticated imagery, obtained from forensic devices and document readers (DE04, ¶ 64-65). Document experts can exchange details on a same level of knowledge and expertise (DE05, ¶ 86). It would be useful to link second and third level experts (DE06, ¶ 7) or create a hierarchy of experts for automated escalation in case of expert unavailability (DE06, ¶ 130). Experts would more often request second opinions from foreign experts (DE09, ¶ 94-95). The platform does not necessarily have to interlink international experts – it could also just link national experts from different sites (EX02, ¶ 13). Referring to the JET action weeks and national helpdesk, a platform could also interlink those helpdesks (EX07, ¶ 46). International Experts are more familiar with local document details such as Spelling mistakes or details within addresses, for example, if the house number is written before or after the street (SC03, item 12).

4.3.5 Case “Rights, Permits and Visa Consulting”

This study focusses on the authentication of IDs and only has a loose connection with rights, permits and visas. I nevertheless want to share the findings about those topics because the mechanics of a remote consultation are similar to those of the document helpdesks.

The codes that are used to describe visa details are exhaustive and not easily understood. They can be obtained in 28-page long PDFs which are hard to use on a mobile device. It would be beneficial for police officers if they could easily connect to a helpdesk which could decode those visa formalities upon request (DE06, ¶ 35). Other areas that require special knowledge are heavy goods transport, freight transports, dangerous goods and related permits (DE09, ¶ 105). Staff at airports must know details about EU legislation: can a person with a residence permit for Czech Republic enter Germany? They could share their knowledge with staff that is less exposed to such questions (EX08, ¶ 29). A similar example provided PP05 while talking about Schengen legislation. Employees in offices have the knowhow and patrol police in the street the need for it (¶ 33). SC01 mentioned service centers assisting police officers in the assessment of a factual situation, providing legal aid and in which order certain measures can be applied.

4.3.6 Case “Imposter Detection”

Also just remotely related to document authentication is the specific case of impostor detection. An Identity Document is the root of trust between attribute such as name, date of birth, place of birth, country of birth and a person, because it unifies the personal data with the image of the holder on a trusted, governmental issued document (personal communication, OVD Kinegram AG).

Germany began educating registration authorities and driving license offices in impostor detection so that they can recognize impostors (EX07, ¶ 65). A remote impostor detection consultant could inspect the picture printed onto the passport, obtained from the chip of the passport and a picture captured on the spot and return an assessment. The right consultant can be chosen because it is assigned to the same organisation or by distance to the submitter. (EX08, ¶ 21).

5 Discussion / Conclusions

This dissertation seeks to identify stakeholders, assess success factors, and find concrete use cases for platform-based collaboration in international law enforcement authenticating identity documents. The answer to the research question “Can platform-based international police collaboration simplify the authentication of identity documents?” is “Yes” and I will now conclude the results and discuss the findings.

5.1 Key Findings of This Dissertation

There are three main use cases for platform-based collaboration to simplify document the authentication of identity documents for stakeholders such as police officers, document experts, executives, public organizations and international police:

1. **“Data Verification”**: A technology platform would allow police officers to fetch data from a third country to verify if (a) a document was issued in the first place, (b) the data is authentic and ideally (c) if the picture of the holder matches the picture on the document. This case will be difficult to build because study participants see many hurdles with data protection.
2. **“Guided Assistance”**: A transactional platform would allow police officers to request legally unbinding consulting and remote support from helpdesks. The helpdesk would support the police officer in detecting hints for fraudulent documents through (a) voice commands, (b) picture exchange and (c) the combination of smartphones and tools such as magnifiers. This case seems feasible, provided that the idea is supported by the management and the right starting point is identified.
3. **“Collaborative Knowledge Base”**: A content platform which would allow international experts to combine their knowledge and findings about authentic and fake documents as well as anomalies in one system. Police Officers and later Municipalities could access the knowledge base as a self-service portal. Criminal Investigation would learn from the data and investigate patterns. This case bears the risk that data and details about authentic documents could get in the wrong hands if the platform is operated too open or not governed correctly.

5.2 Conclusion of The Nine Success Dimensions of Digital Platforms

The following sections conclude the results from the assessment of the different dimensions investigated through the study. They are sorted according to their importance in a descending order.

5.2.1 “Governance” Factor Stands Neutral to Positive Towards Platform-Based Collaboration. No preferred operator emerged from the interviews. Some consider state owned or any trustworthy company from the private sector capable. Others prefer Frontex due to their existing services which may be expanded to platform-based use cases. Depending on the final scope of the platform – whether it will offer its services to European or global participants, it should be governed by Europol, Interpol or even ICAO. The platform should be closed rather than open, only allowing police organisations which were approved through “some kind of committee” access to its services. Document Experts should follow minimum standards for document and identification verification and could prove their expertise through an exam, training, updates, and field experience. Different roles such as ‘users’ or ‘document experts’ and transparency about the platform’s structure and processes builds trust among the participants. Participants should be authenticated, at least through username, password, and mail address of their police organization. Ideally, the platform would operate with intelligent access management where users are authenticated through their organization’s identity management solution. The platform would regulate interactions that already take place but are not managed by an administration to date. The participants are not in agreement on the question of whether companies should be able to join as well, and a workaround could be the segmentation through different access and service levels (4.1.1).

5.2.2 “Stakeholders” Factor Stands Neutral to Positive Towards Platform-Based Collaboration. There are numerous national and international stakeholders that must be considered throughout the project. Crucial Stakeholders are Interpol, Europol, Frontex, SIRENE, data protection officers, existing international police helpdesks, Federal Police and politicians because a new platform would harmonize, expand or compete their existing processes and practises. Existing international groups such as high-level roundtables, PCC-SEE, ICAO are important and should participate together with national police, cantonal police, administrations,

and subject-matter experts. Involved stakeholders are the citizens, which's IDs are authenticated, industry specific companies such as device manufacturers and industries which benefit from ID authentication because of the damages caused by fake IDs, such as banking, car rentals and aviation.

The ideal management team does not emerge from the data. The management team could consist of Frontex, the European Commission, Europol, and Interpol. Municipalities were mentioned, which can be represented through their police organisations. Domain experts such as border guards and customs should be represented, too. The management team may even be segmented, if the platform is organized in federated but interlinked systems. The top-management of the platform and related stakeholders must provide their full support because the platform would not be used otherwise.

Within law enforcement, access to the platform should not be exclusive. From patrol police, second line, forensic expert to government departments, counter fraud units and border guards plus customs – “every law enforcement agency” should be able to access and use ID authentication services provided by the experts on the platform. Within the Interpol member states, some violate human rights or may use the platform to exfiltrate information about the manufacturing processes of security elements, hence they are considered undesired participants.

Primary customer groups are police organisations, customs, border guards and municipalities, migration offices, notaries, foreigners' authorities, driver's license offices, weapon authorities and consulates. Commercial entities are considered a secondary customer group because a lot of economic damage can be avoided for little additional costs if crimes caused by fake IDs are prevented (4.1.2).

5.2.3 “Value Proposition” Factor Stands Positive Towards Platform-Based Collaboration. The conclusion about the value proposition of a platform for ID authentication is derived from the three most important use cases which are described in detail within chapter 4.3 on page 58. In the case of “Data Verification”, a police officer would use a subset of name, dates, and document numbers to determine if an ID was issued in that given combination. He could check if it is marked wanted, lost, or stolen. Ideally, the original picture for the document holder would be transferred to the officer for him to detect replacements of pictures or misuse of an ID

by a lookalike. The platform would automate data exchange (through defined processes and secure connections), and if personal data may not be transferred due to data protection concerns, a simple “true” or “false” reply could already be sufficient. This platform would support existing processes, decrease process time and increase efficiency.

In the case “Guided Assistance”, the police officer would request consultation about an unfamiliar or doubtful ID from document experts. The document expert could be reached easily through automatic matchmaking, which follows rules, for example preferring experts from the own organization or country over others. An officer would spend less time looking for hints cumbersome PDFs or online databases and could focus on his main tasks. The expertise of the expert would be transferred to the police officer over distance and (managed) image exchange would make communication easier compared to traditional voice assistance. This would reduce undesired wait time, avoid inconvenience for the checked person and support the police officer through a second assessment.

The “Expert Exchange” through a platform would mainly provide fast and efficient exchange of findings around forgery series between organizational, national, or even international experts and even helpdesks.

5.2.4 “Strategic Management” Factor Stands Positive Towards Platform-Based Collaboration. The topic of platform-based collaboration is not new for international law enforcement. The German Federal Police launched the project JETs (Joint Expert Teams) which provides remote assistance “by mail”. Binational helpdesks foster document authentication and data verification. Language barriers are tackled through bilingual forms. This is a great base to work with. There are also ideas to develop existing ‘read-only’ reference databases into collaborative tools.

The participants consider “direct data query” to be the most important functionality, followed up by remote consultation for ID authenticity verification (or rather, counterfeit detection, which is more feasible remotely). The platform should link experts with police officers by making it easy to find the right person, reach out quickly and support foreign authorities, too.

The search for a first mover or early adopter will be short as most participants are eager to support the platform from the beginning. One condition is that it was

approved through the hierarchy and the critical aspects such as data protection are taken care of. There are different opinions about the starting point: Some would multiply the existing concept of binational helpdesks and JET action weeks, others would expand existing platforms such as FADO (which is a European software), and some would start from scratch, working on the international data query as a first module and expand from there. Some would start with one organization, others with countries, others see the “big bang” approach as the right approach.

Experts agree that the strategic goal of the platform is to reduce crime across borders through collaboration and that ideally, patterns of origin of fraud are uncovered and criminal activities are stopped at an early level. Collaboration should be speed up, security increased and existing exchange becomes institutionalized.

To approve a such a platform, it must be built by the right organisations, people, and through the right methods. The business case must be clearly defined and supported by data protection officers. A crucial prerequisite is the secure encrypted transfer, storage, and processing of personal data. “Data” must be clearly specified and may or may not include pictures or other biometric information about the people with the questioned document. The user groups must be specified because different (non-) police organizations operate under different jurisdiction. Existing stakeholders (and solution providers) must be onboarded at an early stage to fight redundancies without endangering established processes (4.1.3).

5.2.5 “IT Architecture” Factor Stands Neutral to Positive Towards Platform-Based Collaboration. There are existing Systems and Databases which could be combined through a platform. International systems include FIELDS with the much-appreciated Quick Check Cards, iFADO, PRADO, “Schengen Information System”, I-24, Interpol SLTD, SIENA. National systems include ARKILA, D232, DOKIS, “Informationssystem Urkunde”, “Länderinformations- und Erkenntnisssystem”, Argus and others, such as eLearning platforms. There are many redundancies and organizations use but also maintain multiple similar databases.

Even if there are differences in the equipment of portable devices, platform-based interactions are possible as most police forced carry a business smartphone. There is a mix of iPhones and Android devices. While some still have tablets, others stopped using them. Data connectivity may be a problem, depending on the location.

There is heterogeneity in the document authentication tool area. Most police have a torch with white light as personal equipment or at least in their car or at the next outpost. Cars and outposts often provide extra light sources such as UV, too. Magnifiers are not a standard and often have to be bought in an officer's own interest. Smartphone magnifying capabilities improved recently, which would support the platform-based remote assistance case.

Police officers barely have a personal laptop, especially when on duty in the streets. More 'border related' organizations or people with specific training often have access to a laptop or computer, which is connected to police networks and additional sources of information.

Forensic devices such as document readers with multiple light sources, binoculars and high-resolution scanners are usually only found within reach of document experts or helpdesks. While they are required for authenticity checks, to which a document must be brought in anyway, a first consultation would not require such sophisticated equipment for police officers.

Study participants mentioned that a basic set of equipment (white-light- and UV torches, and magnifiers) would be beneficial for document authentication. In the future, its desirable to connect business smartphones with magnifiers so that the police officer can directly capture high-resolution images for experts.

A variety of police apps is available to exchange messages, query data, access reference databases and capture images. Nations do have a different technology level. Public apps should not be used for police work. There are nevertheless occasions where private e-mail addresses or public instant messaging apps are used.

Access to specific police networks is restricted and some authorities are not connected to police networks. Signal strength may be a challenge in remote or roaming areas (4.2.1).

5.2.6 “Marketing and Communication” were Only Briefly Assessed. Communication about the project and the platform is crucial. A platform will not be used if the parties are unaware of it. Its value proposition must be tangible for every participant, from police officer (getting faster feedback) to document experts (getting more insights) to executives (increased efficiency) (4.2.2).

5.2.7 “Enterprise Culture” Factor Stands Positive Towards Platform-Based Collaboration. The personal mindset towards document authentication varies: The motivation to check identity documents depends on training and personal interest of the police officer. Some experts love their job, others use the niche knowledge to support their career. From those who love it, many go an extra mile to support their colleagues, even after business hours.

Digital readiness increases overall. Young employees are more open to work with new, digital solutions than older or more experienced employees, of which some are still keen to use it. There are differences between different countries but from the technological point of view, prerequisites for platform-based collaboration are met.

Most participants are willing to collaborate through a platform and some platform-based interactions already take place on a national, but not an international level. The working-environment and the human factor influence the willingness to collaborate through a platform. Acceptance is boosted if it's a smartphone-based solution, introduced as an add-on to something that already exists (4.2.3).

5.2.8 “Pricing Structure” Factor Stands Neutral to Positive Towards Platform-Based Collaboration. Costs and benefits should be analysed, and the business model must be clear before a decision about the funding is made. The fact that costs occur at the ministries of interior while the benefits impact the social sector may be a challenge for the business model, which need to be understood by the decisive bodies.

The platform could be funded through lump-sums of interested bodies or through joint funding such as EU projects (which have the disadvantage that projects end after seven years). Governments and private companies should work and invests together, which may lead to a higher price but a sooner readiness. The business case must also clarify whether organizations, nations or on a modular base even individual cantons and “Bundesländer” or police organizations are invoiced.

As police agencies tend to not invoice across border, the concept of transaction fees was perceived controversially as they can defeat the purpose of an international platform. Asymmetries in demand and supply may lead to small participants (needing most support) to run out of money the quickest. Experts consider their services paid through their salary and police officers would question the utility of the platform.

Services within an EU / Schengen project must be offered, regardless of the costs. Nevertheless, transaction fees would be beneficial if ‘hidden in the back’: They could support the budgeting process, fictional billing, increase cost transparency, would enable pay-per-use models, and support expanding of document verification services to authorities or commercial entities such as airlines, banks, or car rental companies. Instead of invoicing transactions, they could be regarded as contingents. If dynamic transactions fees must be excluded from a platform, participating organizations could cover costs through more traditional licensing models (4.2.4).

5.2.9 “Legislation and Regulation” Stands Neutral but Challenging Towards Platform-Based Collaboration. Different data protection laws and regulations are considered the biggest showstopper for the platform, but participants see a chance in making the platform happen. Data can be shared if purpose and the way data is shared is defined. Technical measures may help to handle data but the risk of providing too much data through aggregation of different sources remains.

Firstly, the legal basis for the collection, handling, exchange, and processing of data must be established through “Errichtungsanordnung” (Statutory Order of Establishment), terms and conditions and IT security policies. For countries outside Schengen area, new international contracts are required. There are additional contracts between Europol, Frontex and third countries. It must be decided if the platform would offer police assistance (non-binding) or legal aid (binding). The data should remain within the control of the police systems and not spread throughout private companies.

Data protection laws are there for a good reason – queries should only be allowed if it is guaranteed that the prospect is not endangered through a data query because the provider of data is not always known, and some countries still apply death penalties.

Today, international police collaboration requires a single point of contact, which is mostly established through the nations federal police. A platform could support processes which guide queries from city police to cantonal police to federal police, ensuring rightful queries with the extra benefit of efficient, well-defined processes and compliance with data traceability.

It is unlikely that a platform would offer legally binding remote document authenticity checks through experts, but it seems possible that it would support effective document forgery consulting for the frontline. One way to overcome

problems with data protection laws in the “Guided Assistance” case would be an automated censoring of personal details before a request for support is submitted. It would be possible to inspect layout, fonts and techniques, damages, and manipulation attempts. On the other hand, the censoring would obscure relevant areas and make it impossible to find impostors or query databases, as described in case “Data Verification” (4.2.5).

5.3 Discussion of the Results

The study confirmed that police officers and document experts can be regarded as parties of a two sided “market” (2.2.2 & 4.3.2). This market provides transactions for identity (document) authentication or consultation, which happen on- or offline (2.3.3 & 4.2.1). Also, the roles of manager and sponsor emerged in the study, represented through “the management team” and (private) companies providing technology (2.3.4 & 4.1.2). International police support is more structured and regulated thus needs less matchmaking support compared to C2C B2C or B2B markets. G2G platforms could however benefit from matchmaking, if internal processes are respected and existing hierarchies are considered, matching local user groups before considering national or even international peers (2.3.6 & 4.1.1). The study confirmed that the value propositions found in literature (efficiency, lower friction, lower transaction- and coordination costs) would also apply for ID authentication. The positive impact on organizational capacity was not confirmed (2.3.3 & 4.3).

Four of the six emergent use cases (“Guided Assistance”, “Experts Exchange”, “Rights, Permits and Visa Consulting” and “Impostor Detection”) suit a transaction/mediation platform model because the platform would connect “customers” with “suppliers”. The two remaining cases (“Data Verification” and “Collaborative Knowledge Base”) relate to product-technology or collaborative content platforms (2.3.1 & 4.3).

Theory states that matchmakers should be paid for their services of providing thick markets and transaction fees that relate to the transaction value can be applied. The data shows that transaction fees are perceived controversially by the participants of the study. If the platform would be opened for G2B transactions, the fees for business entities seem more applicable (2.3.11 & 4.2.4).

Platforms support matchmaking and establish trust between unknown entities in C2C environments. Law enforcement heavily relies on personal contacts and the trust would not come through the platform (providing rating systems) but rather from the association of a member and its relation to the official law enforcement organization (2.2.5 & 4.1.1).

A last discrepancy between literature and the result of this study is that literature considers the success dimension “Legislation and Regulation” only responsible for 2% of successful and 3% of failed platform projects, while it is international regulations and especially data protection laws are crucial in the context of international law enforcement and identity (document) authentication (2.4 & 4.2.5).

5.4 Limitations and Weaknesses of this Study

The general methodology served their purpose. The questions helped to research the problem statement throughout nine important dimensions and the derived knowledge should provide the participants with food for thought. The assumed interview roles that emerged from the initial stakeholder analysis with the customer had to be adjusted because I could not access to any “IT-Administrators”. Instead, three service centers signed up for the study which provided even better insights about ongoing collaboration. The chosen samples provided reliable and differentiated insights about ongoing international collaboration. I was overwhelmed by the amount of interest generated by the study. Although there were 27 participants from 11 countries, the study only covers a section of the countries. Even with those 11 countries, we only scratched on the surface of how European law enforcement collaborates. The study only has insights about a fraction of the EMEA region, and no data about NA, LATAM, and APAC. While it is great to see that there are common denominators between different European participants representing the same role, The study does not necessarily represent “all document experts” or all “police officers” and their different national situations. However, the different measures of validations (Stakeholders, Interview Questions, Interview Guides, and Coding and even asking every participant about their opinion about the interview for quality assurance) improve validity, reliability of the results and that they are relevant for the participants of this study, even if the findings cannot be generalized to a global scale.

5.5 Ethical Implications of this Study

This is not a typical business administration research due to the special industry. The main stakeholders are the interview participants, their (law enforcement) organisations, my sponsor, the Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts and myself. The participants shared important details with me, and it is in the interest of the participants that the raw data is kept confidential. As communicated with the study invitation, the participants will receive the results and are able to use and share at their own will. The raw data was only stored on personal devices with access protection. By the time of writing, all raw data is either (a) permanently deleted or (b) protected with a password. The participants desire reliable and valid results and I therefore only used disclosed sources and scientific methods to process available literature and primary data. No data was manipulated to reach a given conclusion. I follow the no-harm to participants principle which means that I give the participants the opportunity to participate anonymously, avoided harmful questions and only use the data in the interest of this study, which does not pursue an evil goal in general. Consent is achieved through transparency about the aim of the research, procedures of gathering, processing, and storing data, publication of the results, and the avoidance of the possibility of pinning back details to a participant. Mutuality is achieved by providing the results of this study to all participants. I am not aware of any part of this work which would conflict with human rights. I am not aware of conflicts of interests, as I work from the perspective of a student and my employer / customer does not offer collaboration-platforms. Okay, maybe “not yet”. It would make me proud if I could be involved in the development of such a platform, therefore the results may be biased.

5.6 Practical and Theoretical Importance of the Findings

While previous research has focussed on platforms in the C2C, B2C or B2B sector, these results show that digital platforms can also provide value in the international law enforcement area through increased efficiency. Operative document authentication is a niche industry and narrowly researched, although costs that come from misuse of identities or forged identity documents is significant. From a practical perspective, the study sheds light on the factors influencing platforms and found three use cases that can now be followed-up by the executives from the area. The findings suggest that independent systems could be combined into few platforms and that

national regulations which prevent global platforms could be overcome through breaking it down to smaller, localized units. The results should be considered when future strategic activities towards the simplification of international collaboration in law enforcement are discussed.

From the theoretical standpoint, this study contributes to a broader understanding of how G2G platforms would differ from commercial platforms, because certain success dimension, especially governance with trust and pricing structure with transaction-based billing differs significantly from those in other commercial platforms.

Overall, the practical implications of this study provide actionable guidance for practitioners seeking to enhance collaboration through digital platforms, while the theoretical contributions offer valuable insights that expand the knowledge for platform-based collaboration in law enforcement.

6 Recommendation

The value of this study may be left unexploited if no recommendations are derived from the results, the conclusion, and the discussion. In this chapter, I add direct and decisive recommendations based on justified choices. I firstly summarize organisational recommendations then share my thoughts about technical findings before ending with recommendations for future research.

6.1 Organisational Recommendation

We learned that international collaboration is useful to overcome uncertainty with unfamiliar documents but international collaboration (and even national collaboration through different organisations can be difficult to establish. While general platform models apply to use cases found in this study, a final solution is far from found. Because big IT systems can be complicated and complex to develop, and many different stakeholders have to be considered, I strongly recommend using a lean product development approach like “Lean Innovation” from Dr. David Griesbach (2023). More importantly, a steering committee of top-level supporters should be assembled that scope the initial scope of a platform. While we’ve seen different start and growth strategies in the results, I consider a national scope of an European member a good starting point, because it would enable lean growth throughout the Schengen

are and avoid difficult contracts between countries that are too far off. This steering committee would then decide which use case should be addressed first. Although the “Data Verification” case was mentioned most, it implies difficulties with data protection and automated data exchange over multiple, maybe disconnected networks. I would therefore address the “Guided Assistance” case first. From there, the right partner for the technical development can be evaluated, where I recommend a company with ties to the industry and an advance in trust. Funding may be obtained through an innovation project from the government or even co-sponsored by the company. The whole ecosystem must be considered from minute one, as unnecessary powerplays, competition and conflicts with existing systems must be avoided. Synergies must be sought instead. Then, a sustainable business model should be developed, along with drafts of detailed use cases, processes, and requirements before even the first line of code is written.

6.2 Technical Recommendation

A technical recommendation is hard to write as the platform is a concept which can be realized in many ways. To avoid getting lost in technicalities which may be obsolete by the time a platform is effectively built (as the moving target may shift during the lean innovation approach), I recommend pursuing multiple different ideas that came up during the writing of this thesis. Data protection is a crucial part of international collaboration with identity documents and centralized data silos / lakes are hard to handle and represent a honeypot for criminals. Instead of accumulating a big database of identity related snippets through independent transactions, it should be verified if each transaction can be encrypted through a private & public key mechanism which would only allow the involved parties and its proxies (such as supervisors) access to the data within the transaction. Furthermore, it must not be the goal to develop “the one big” platform – instead the concept of decentralisation should be considered: A platform may operate stand-alone, in a hierarchy (of national instances) or in a mesh (of top-level national instances being interlinked with each other). Although the study reveals that the platform should be rather closed from a customer and supplier point of view, it may be open for third party developers providing modules, covering different use cases. In that way, I feel that it should be possible to connect existing user management systems with even low hierarchy level platform and enable a secure trusted transaction throughout multiple levels. The

sponsors of the technology could consider a hybrid platform approach, where they offer system modules (for authentication, certificate, messaging, networking, ...) and the third parties would provide specific use case related modules (such as data verification, knowledge base, and guided assistance). This may even enable interoperability between existing systems and the new platform.

Figure 11 Network of Platforms (Own Illustration)

6.3 Recommendation for Future Research

From an organisational point of view, the research only covers a small section of European participants. It would be beneficial investigate how other European regions or maybe the LATAM region perceives the situation. Also, a case study with

the same questions but just one organisation would be a great base to start lean development.

From the technical perspective, I suggest follow up on this research by researching feasibility of decentral platform networks or how blockchain-based storage technology such as Storj (*Storj - Make the World Your Data Center*, n.d.) support secure decentralized content platforms.

Bibliography / References

- | *KURSANGEBOT*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 6, 2022, from <https://www.edupolice.ch/de/kurse/kursangebot>
- Antonio. (2022, July 18). Il Falsario V Edizione 31-Agosto 2022 Palazzo della Gran Guardia Verona. *Polizia Locale*. <https://polizialocale.org/il-falsario-v-edizione-31-agosto-2022-palazzo-della-gran-guardia-verona/>
- Belleflamme, P., & Peitz, M. (2021). *The economics of platforms: Concepts and strategy*. Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/9781108696913>
- Biernacki, P., & Waldorf, D. (1981). Snowball Sampling: Problems and Techniques of Chain Referral Sampling. *Sociological Methods & Research*, 10(2), 141–163. <https://doi.org/10.1177/004912418101000205>
- Bika, N. (2016, July 8). *15 collaboration tools for productive teams*. Recruiting Resources: How to Recruit and Hire Better. <https://resources.workable.com/tutorial/collaboration-tools>
- Brown, K. (n.d.). *Law enforcement change tactics to combat fake IDs made overseas*. <https://www.fox19.com>. Retrieved December 4, 2022, from <https://www.fox19.com/2022/09/13/law-enforcement-change-tactics-combat-fake-ids-made-overseas/>
- Bügler, J. (n.d.). *Wie das LKA gefälschte Ausweise entdeckt—110—Das Polzeimagazin—YouTube*. Retrieved February 24, 2023, from <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gmQnJfFJsE&t=129s>
- Bundespolizei Karriere (Director). (2021, January 13). *Bundespolizei JETs In Action*. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1qkRI4fDYiQ>
- Bundespolizeipräsidium Organisationsplan*. (2022, August 3). <https://www.bundespolizei.de/Web/DE/05Die->

Bundespolizei/03Organisation/01Praesidium/organigramm_file.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=33

Careers in Questioned Documents | *American Academy of Forensic Sciences*. (n.d.).

Retrieved December 6, 2022, from <https://www.aaafs.org/careers-questioned-documents>

Deegan, K., & Kotchick, B. A. (2021). Factors Associated With Owning a Fake ID: Personality Traits and Problematic Alcohol Use. *Psi Chi Journal of Psychological Research*, 26(2), 176–184. <https://doi.org/10.24839/2325-7342.JN26.2.176>

Defensie, M. van. (2017, May 15). *Identity fraud and document expertise—Travel documents—Defensie.nl* [Onderwerp]. Ministerie van Defensie. <https://english.defensie.nl/topics/travel-documents/identity-fraud-and-safe-airports>

Document authentication. (n.d.). Retrieved December 4, 2022, from <https://www.verifai.com/en/document-authentication/>

Eisenmann, T., Parker, G., & Alstynne, M. W. V. (2006). Strategies for Two-Sided Markets. *Harvard Business Review*.

Evans, D. S., & Schmalensee, R. (2016). *Matchmakers: The new economics of multisided platforms*. Harvard Business Review Press.

Fake ID Usage in the U.S. (Survey). (2019, March 27). Greenhouse Treatment Center. <https://greenhousetreatment.com/blog/news/fake-id-usage-survey/>

Forensic Document Examination Experts | *GBG IDscan*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 6, 2022, from <https://www.gbGPLC.com/en/products/id-document-verification/forensic-document-experts/>

- Gawer, A. (2009). *Platforms, Markets and Innovation*. Edward Elgar Publishing.
<https://doi.org/10.4337/9781849803311>
- Gillies, B. (2022, August 2). *How Common Are Fake IDs?* IDScan.Net.
<https://idscan.net/how-common-are-fake-ids/>
- Grad Coach (Director). (2022, January 27). *Qualitative Coding Tutorial: How To Code Qualitative Data For Analysis (4 Steps + Examples)*.
https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8MHkVtE_sVw
- Griesbach, D. (2023, May 25). *Lean Innovation Guide*.
<https://www.orellfuessli.ch/shop/home/artikeldetails/A1067368444>
- Heck, E. van, & Vervest, P. (2007). Smart business networks: How the network wins. *Communications of the ACM*, 50(6), 28–37.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/1247001.1247002>
- Home. *Die-dokumentenexperten.de*. (n.d.). Retrieved December 9, 2022, from
<https://www.die-dokumentenexperten.de/>
- Jacobson, I. (2004). Use cases – Yesterday, today, and tomorrow. *Software & Systems Modeling*, 3(3), 210–220. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10270-004-0060-3>
- Kostova, D., & Institut za izsledvane na občestvata i znaniето (Eds.). (2014). *Institutional trust*. Prof. Marin Drinov Academic Publishing House.
- McAfee, A., Brynjolfsson, E., & McAfee, A. (2018). *Machine, Platform, Crowd: Wie wir das Beste aus unserer digitalen Zukunft machen* (P. Seedorf, Trans.). Plassen Verlag.
- MDR Investigativ (Director). (2021, March 20). *Deals mit gefälschten Pässen*.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iIVGRcxfNY>
- Millar, G. (2021). *Writing Dissertations: A Guide*. Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts.

https://elearning.hslu.ch/ilias/goto.php?target=file_5536144_download&client_id=hslu

- Muffatto, M. (1999). Introducing a platform strategy in product development. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 60–61, 145–153. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-5273\(98\)00173-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0925-5273(98)00173-X)
- Özcan, L., Koldewey, C., Duparc, E., Valk, H. van der, Otto, B., & Dumitrescu, R. (2022). Why do Digital Platforms succeed or fail? - A Literature Review on Success and Failure Factors. *AMCIS 2022 Proceedings*, 11.
- Parker, G., Van Alstyne, M., & Choudary, S. P. (2017). *Platform revolution: How networked markets are transforming the economy - and how to make them work for you* (First published as a Norton paperback 2017). W. W. Norton & Company.
- Polizei Schweiz Voraussetzungen: Anforderungen im Überblick*. (2019, May 20). <https://polizist-karriere.ch/polizei-voraussetzungen/>
- Rochet, J.-C., & Tirole, J. (2003). Platform Competition in Two-Sided Markets. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 1(4), 990–1029. <https://doi.org/10.1162/154247603322493212>
- Rogers, E. M. (2003). *Diffusion of innovations* (5th ed). Free Press.
- Rysman, M. (2009). The Economics of Two-Sided Markets. *The Journal of Economic Perspectives*, 23(3), 125–143.
- Saunders, B., Kitzinger, J., & Kitzinger, C. (2015). Anonymising interview data: Challenges and compromise in practice. *Qualitative Research*, 15(5), 616–632. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1468794114550439>
- Schaedler, René. (2021, March 16). *Street-Police_Passport-Verification.jpg (JPEG-Grafik, 920 × 614 Pixel)*. KINEGRAM - Home.

https://www.kinegram.com/fileadmin/_processed_/d/d/csm_2021_03_16_OVD_SecurityPersonal_D853041_MobileChip_SDK_30dd61b083.jpg

Sepuru, M., Musonda, I., & Okoro, C. S. (2021). An Assessment of Factors Influencing Collaboration Impacts on Organisational Performance: A Review. In S. M. Ahmed, P. Hampton, S. Azhar, & A. D. Saul (Eds.), *Collaboration and Integration in Construction, Engineering, Management and Technology* (pp. 321–325). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-48465-1_54

shribe! - master your studies (Director). (2019, June 2). *Qualitative Inhaltsanalyse nach Mayring (7-Schritte-Tutorial)*

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ky8w7rqvEEo>

Spain | OSCE POLIS. (n.d.). Retrieved December 7, 2022, from <https://polis.osce.org/country-profiles/spain>

Startseite. (n.d.). Retrieved December 6, 2022, from <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/de/>

Steinberg, M. (2019). *The platform economy: How Japan transformed the consumer Internet*. University of Minnesota Press.

Storj—Make the world your data center. (n.d.). Retrieved June 7, 2023, from <https://www.storj.io/>

Tätigkeiten—Tätigkeiten. (n.d.). Retrieved February 24, 2023, from <https://www.gr.ch/DE/institutionen/verwaltung/djsg/kapo/ueberuns/organisation/polizeiberuf/taetigkeiten/Seiten/default.aspx>

Terrill, B. J., & Flitman, A. (2004). A Qualitative Method for Identifying Factors that Influence User Satisfaction. In H. Linger, J. Fisher, W. Wojtkowski, W. G. Wojtkowski, J. Zupančič, K. Vigo, & J. Arnold (Eds.), *Constructing the*

Infrastructure for the Knowledge Economy (pp. 293–304). Springer US.

https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-4852-9_21

Voraussetzungen. (n.d.). Polizei Hessen Karriere. Retrieved November 22, 2022, from

<http://karriere.polizei.hessen.de/icc/karriere/nav/202/broker.jsp?uMen=20201>

023-0000-1111-2222-111111110001

▷ *Eignungstest Polizei Zürich: Alle Infos zum Einstellungstest*. (2018, September 14).

<https://polizist-karriere.ch/eignungstest-polizei-zuerich/>

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Appendix A Stakeholder Analysis for Participants

The first alignment with Andreas Schilling lead to three main stakeholders, which would interact with a platform for ID authentication: Patrol police, document experts, and executives. IT administrators were invited to participate as well because IT architecture occurs as a success factor in 8% and as a failure factor in 19% of the literature (Özcan et al., 2022, p. 4).

During the participant gathering process, I noticed that no IT-administrators signed up, but I learned about the existence of service centers, which I then addressed as a fourth group instead of the ID-administrators. In general, I was overwhelmed by the amount of participants by country and by expert perspective:

Figure 12 A1 Numbers of Participants per Expert Perspective

Table 2 A1 Participants by Role and Count

Role	Count
Strategy/Exec	10
Doc Expert	9
Front Policing	5
Service Center	3
Total	27

Figure 13 A2 Number of Participants by Country

Table 3 A2 Participants by Country and Count

Number	Country	Count
1	Germany	8
2	Switzerland	6
3	Austria	2
4	Netherlands	2
5	Ukraine	2
6	United Kingdom	2
7	Estonia	1
8	Greece	1
9	Italy	1
10	Lithuania	1
11	Poland	1
	Total	27

Appendix B “Why do Digital Platforms succeed or fail?”

Figure 14 B Nine Success Dimensions by Özcan et al.

Note. From “Why do Digital Platforms succeed or fail? - A Literature Review on Success and Failure Factors”, by Özcan et al., 2022, *AMCIS 2022 Proceedings*, p. 3 (https://aisel.aisnet.org/amcis2022/sig_dite/sig_dite/15)

Table 4 B Success Dimensions and Mentions in %

dimension	success %	aggr. %	failure %	aggr. %	Average %
governance	23	23	16	16	19.5
stakeholder mgmt.	20	43	19	35	19.5
value proposition	19	62	13	48	16
strategic mgmt.	13	75	19	67	16
IT-architecture	8	83	19	86	13.5
marketing communication	6	89	0	86	3
enterprise culture	6	95	3	89	4.5
pricing structure	3	98	8	97	5.5
legislation and regulation	2	100	3	100	2.5

Appendix C Study invitation

The participants were invited using a study invitation, which was “validated” for simplicity, understandability and effectiveness by the marketing department.

Interview Invitation

Can international police-to-police remote-support simplify the authentication of identity documents?

Desired participants are

- **Front Police**
- **Document Experts**
- **Data Protection Officers**
- **IT-Administrators**

Please reach out to Stefan.Gabriel@kinegram.com, **+41 (0) 41 555 21 43** before Friday, 17 February 2023 for further information and appointment coordination.

In my master's thesis, I am investigating whether remote support from one police force to another helps to check foreign passports, driver's licenses and other identity cards on the spot. I want to find use cases for this kind of international collaboration and identify factors that influence its implementation.

- **Max. 1 hour interview**
- **Online or in person**
- **Must take place between 06 and 31 March 2023**

Participants will receive the study and are invited to use and share the findings.

Appendix D Preparation of Interview Questions

This table shows how the interview questions were mapped to Özcan et al.'s (2022) success and failure dimensions. The first row describes their dimension, the second row the question and the last rows in which interview guide the question was added. “g” stands for “general questions” such as warm-up or ending questions. “x” means that the question is included in the role-specific interview guide. “?” stands for “this question may be asked additionally”.

Table 5 D Mapping of Dimensions and Questions

Category (relevance acc. To Özcan et al.)	Question	Patrol Police (20)	Document Expert (21)	Executive (21)	Service Center (21)
	Which of the following roles does describe you best? (1) Front Police, (2) Document Expert, (3) Executive, (4) Service Center	g	g	g	g
Introduction	What is your motivation to support this study?	g	g	g	g
Introduction	How did you get into the law-enforcement industry?	g	g	g	g
governance (19.5%)	How should new participants be approved onto the platform?		x	x	x
governance (19.5%)	Would you trust a foreign document expert?	x		x	
governance (19.5%)	Considering the international collaboration aspect - who should be in charge of operating such a platform?			x	x
governance (19.5%)	Who should in your oppinion participate in such a platform?		x	x	x
governance (19.5%)	Can you think of downsides if international law-enforcement uses such a platform?	x	x	x	x
stakeholder management (19.5%)	who would you consider stakeholders of such a platform?				x
stakeholder management (19.5%)	which organisation should be part of the management team?				x
stakeholder management (19.5%)	How would your staff react if you woul decide to work towards such a service?				x
value proposition (16%)	How are Ids authenticated today, in a few sentences?	x	x		x
value proposition (16%)	What problems do patrol police have when it comes to ID authentication?	x	x		x
value proposition (16%)	What does patrol police want to know from a document expert using <it>	x			
value proposition (16%)	How often per month is such an interaction required?	x	x		
value proposition (16%)	What is the longest a person should wait for a response?	x	x		x
value proposition (16%)	What functionality must <it> provide to be useful for patrol police?	x	?	?	?
value proposition (16%)	Why would international collaboration through <it> be valuable for you?	x	x	x	x
value proposition (16%)	Please elaborate how you in your role would use <it> in a typical case	x	x		x
value proposition (16%)	What are the consequences of not having <it>?	x	x	x	x
value proposition (16%)	Would you use <it> to share your expert resources with other countries?			x	x
value proposition (16%)	Would you get more help from document experts if one was available easily through <it>?	x	?	?	?
value proposition (16%)	Which important environmental factors must be considered for the use of it (such as weather, stress, network, ...)	x	?	?	?
strategic management (16%)	What are strategic goals towards <it>, if there are any?	x	x	x	x
strategic management (16%)	would you support such a platform by being a 'first mover'?	x	x	x	
strategic management (16%)	What would the most important interaction be which <it> provides?	x	x		
strategic management (16%)	Who is the driving force when it comes to developing <it>?				x
strategic management (16%)	How would you see <it> becoming to life?				x
strategic management (16%)	Whats are prerequisites for you to use or approve the usage of <it>?				x
it architecture (marginal scope, 13.5%)	What standard equipment does every patrol officer have available to exchange data with <it>?	x	x		x
it architecture (marginal scope, 13.5%)	In what order would you sort these technologies for <it>, starting with highest value: (a) picture exchange, (b) direct chat, (c) vi	x	x		x
pricing structure (marginal scope, 5.5%)	How should costs of development and transaction between patrol police and document expert be financed?		x	x	x
pricing structure (marginal scope, 5.5%)	What impact would <it> have, if you (document experts) would get paid for remote support?		x		
pricing structure (marginal scope, 5.5%)	How much does traditional support cost now?		x		
legislation & regulation (marginal scope, 2.5%)	Does <it> have a chance given the current legislations and regulations?		x	x	x
legislation & regulation (marginal scope, 2.5%)	If Data Protection Laws are an issue, could <it> work if for example personal data is automatically censored on device	x	x	x	x
legislation & regulation (marginal scope, 2.5%)	Can document experts be held accountable for their decision?		?	?	x
legislation & regulation (marginal scope, 2.5%)	What is your organisation (not) allowed to capture and send from front police?	x	?		?
enterprise culture (out of scope, 4.5%)	can you say something about police member's digital readiness to use such a platform?	x	x	x	x
enterprise culture (out of scope, 4.5%)	Would members of your organisation collaborate with any other police organisation online?				x
Closing	Is there a reason why <it> will never be established?	g	g	g	g
Closing	What is your impression about this interview?	g	g	g	g
Closing	Would you like to add anything else?	g	g	g	g

Appendix E Interview Guides

POLICE OFFICER / PATROL POLICE

Interviewee		Conducted by	Stefan Gabriel Student at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts
Date		Start Time	End Time

Description of the research: In my master's thesis, I am investigating whether remote support from one police force to another helps to check foreign passports, driver's licenses, and other identity cards on the spot.

Objectives of the research: I want to find use cases for international, platform-based collaboration and investigate key factors that influence its implementation.

Programme: (1) welcome candidate, (2) introduce myself and sponsor of the thesis, (3) introduce the study, (4) inform candidate about confidentiality, anonymity, right to not answer questions, stop interview at any time, ask for consent for recording and processing of data, (5) describe process

Introduction

- What is your motivation to support this study?

Value Proposition

- How are IDs authenticated today, explained in a few sentences?
- What problems do patrol police have when it comes to ID authentication?
- What could patrol police want to know from a document expert using <it>
- How often per month is such an interaction required?
- What is the longest a patrol police should wait for a response?
- What functionality must <it> provide to be useful for patrol police?
- Why would international collaboration through <it> be valuable for you?
- Please elaborate how you in your role would use <it> in a typical case
- What are the consequences of not having <it>?
- Which important environmental factors must be considered for the use of it (such as weather, stress, network, ...)

Governance

- When would you trust a document expert from another country?
- Can you think of downsides if international law-enforcement uses such a platform?

Strategy

- What are strategic goals towards <it>, if there are any?
- would you support such a platform by being a 'first mover'?
- What would the most important interaction be which <it> provides?

Legislation and regulation

- If Data Protection Laws are an issue, could <it> work if for example personal data is automatically censored before transmission to the platform?
- What is your organisation (not) allowed to capture and send from patrol police?

Technology

- What standard equipment does every patrol officer have available to exchange data with <it>?

Corporate culture

- can you say something about police member's digital readiness to use such a platform?
- Would you get more help from document experts if one was available easily through <it>?

Closing

- Is there a reason why <it> will never be established?
- What is your impression about this interview?
- Would you like to add anything else?

Ending: Inform candidate about next steps, processing time, and data processing. Thank you very much for your valuable support!

OVD Kinegram AG, Stefan Gabriel, Zählerweg 11, 6300 Zug, Schweiz

DOCUMENT EXPERT

Interviewee		Conducted by	Stefan Gabriel Student at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts
Date		Start Time	End Time

Description of the research: In my master's thesis, I am investigating whether remote support from one police force to another helps to check foreign passports, driver's licenses, and other identity cards on the spot.

Objectives of the research: I want to find use cases for international, platform-based collaboration and investigate key factors that influence its implementation.

Programme: (1) welcome candidate, (2) introduce myself and sponsor of the thesis, (3) introduce the study, (4) inform candidate about confidentiality, anonymity, right to not answer questions, stop interview at any time, ask for consent for recording and processing of data, (5) describe process

Introduction

- What is your motivation to support this study?

Value Proposition

- How are Ids authenticated today, in a few sentences?
- What problems do patrol police have when it comes to ID authentication?
- How often per month is such an interaction required?
- What is the longest a person should wait for a response?
- Why would international collaboration through <it> be valuable for you?
- Please elaborate how you in your role would use <it> in a typical case
- What are the consequences of not having <it>?

Governance

- Who should in your opinion participate in such a platform?
- How should new participants be approved onto the platform?
- Can you think of downsides if international law-enforcement uses such a platform?

Strategy

- What are strategic goals towards <it>, if there are any?
- Would you support such a platform by being a 'first mover'?
- What would the most important interaction be which <it> provides?

Pricing structure

- How should costs of development and transaction between patrol police and document expert be financed?
- What impact would <it> have, if you (document experts) would get paid for remote support?
- How much does traditional support cost now?

Legislation and regulation

- Does <it> have a chance given the current legislations and regulations?
- If Data Protection Laws are an issue, could <it> work if for example personal data is automatically censored before transmission to the platform?

Technology

- What standard equipment does every patrol officer have available to exchange data with <it>?
- In what order would you sort these technologies for <it>, starting with highest value: (a) picture exchange, (b) direct chat, (c) video calls (d) video capture, (e) direct data query

Corporate culture

- Can you say something about police member's digital readiness to use such a platform?

Closing

- Is there a reason why <it> will never be established?
- What is your impression about this interview?
- Would you like to add anything else?

Ending: Inform candidate about next steps, processing time, and data processing. Thank you very much for your valuable support!

OVD Kinegram AG, Stefan Gabriel, Zählerweg 11, 6300 Zug, Schweiz

EXECUTIVES / MANAGEMENT

Interviewee		Conducted by	Stefan Gabriel Student at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts
Date		Start Time	End Time

Description of the research: In my master's thesis, I am investigating whether remote support from one police force to another helps to check foreign passports, driver's licenses, and other identity cards on the spot.

Objectives of the research: I want to find use cases for international, platform-based collaboration and investigate key factors that influence its implementation.

Programme: (1) welcome candidate, (2) introduce myself and sponsor of the thesis, (3) introduce the study, (4) inform candidate about confidentiality, anonymity, right to not answer questions, stop interview at any time, ask for consent for recording and processing of data, (5) describe process

Introduction

- What is your motivation to support this study?

Value Proposition

- Why would international collaboration through <it> be valuable for you?
- What are the consequences of not having <it>?
- Would you use <it> to share your expert resources with other countries?

Governance

- How should new participants be approved onto the platform?
- When would you trust a document expert from another country?
- Considering the international collaboration aspect - who should oversee operating such a platform?
- Who should in your opinion participate in such a platform?
- Can you think of downsides if international law-enforcement uses such a platform?

Strategy

- What are strategic goals towards <it>, if there are any?
- Would you support such a platform by being a 'first mover'?
- Who is the driving force when it comes to developing <it>?
- How would you see <it> becoming to life?
- What are prerequisites for you to use or approve the usage of <it>?

Stakeholders

- Who would you consider stakeholders of such a platform?
- Which organisation(s) should be part of the management team?
- How would your staff react if you would decide to work towards such a platform?

Pricing structure

- How should costs of development and transaction between patrol police and document expert be financed?

Legislation and regulation

- Does <it> have a chance given the current legislations and regulations?
- If Data Protection Laws are an issue, could <it> work if for example personal data is automatically censored before transmission to the platform?

Corporate culture

- Can you say something about police member's digital readiness to use such a platform?
- Would members of your organisation collaborate with any other police organisation online?

Closing

- Is there a reason why <it> will never be established?
- What is your impression about this interview?
- Would you like to add anything else?

Ending: Inform candidate about next steps, processing time, and data processing. Thank you very much for your valuable support!

OVD Kinegram AG, Stefan Gabriel, Zählerweg 11, 6300 Zug, Schweiz

SERVICE CENTERS

Interviewee		Conducted by	Stefan Gabriel Student at Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts
Date		Start Time	End Time

Description of the research: In my master's thesis, I am investigating whether remote support from one police force to another helps to check foreign passports, driver's licenses, and other identity cards on the spot.

Objectives of the research: I want to find use cases for international, platform-based collaboration and investigate key factors that influence its implementation.

Programme: (1) welcome candidate, (2) introduce myself and sponsor of the thesis, (3) introduce the study, (4) inform candidate about confidentiality, anonymity, right to not answer questions, stop interview at any time, ask for consent for recording and processing of data, (5) describe process

Introduction

- What is your motivation to support this study?

Value Proposition

- How are Ids authenticated today, in a few sentences?
- What problems do patrol police have when it comes to ID authentication?
- What is the longest a person should wait for a response?
- Why would international collaboration through <it> be valuable for you?
- Please elaborate how you in your role would use <it> in a typical case.
- What are the consequences of not having <it>?
- Would you use <it> to share your expert resources with other countries?

Governance

- How should new participants be approved onto the platform?
- Considering the international collaboration aspect - who should oversee operating of such a platform?
- Who should in your opinion participate in such a platform?
- Can you think of downsides if international law-enforcement uses such a platform?

Strategy

- What are strategic goals towards <it>, if there are any?
- Who is the driving force when it comes to developing <it>?
- How would you see <it> becoming to life?

Pricing structure

- How should costs of development and transaction between patrol police and document expert be financed?

Legislation and regulation

- Does <it> have a chance given the current legislations and regulations?
- If Data Protection Laws are an issue, could <it> work if for example personal data is automatically censored on device?
- Can document experts be held accountable for their decision?

Technology

- What standard equipment does every patrol officer have available to exchange data with <it>?
- In what order would you sort these technologies for <it>, starting with highest value: (a) picture exchange, (b) direct chat, (c) video calls (d) video capture, (e) direct data query

Corporate culture

- Can you say something about police member's digital readiness to use such a platform?

Closing

- Is there a reason why <it> will never be established?
- What is your impression about this interview?
- Would you like to add anything else?

Ending: Inform candidate about next steps, processing time, and data processing. Thank you very much for your valuable support!

OVD Kinegram AG, Stefan Gabriel, Zählerweg 11, 6300 Zug, Schweiz

Appendix F List of Interviews Held

Date	Place	Interviewe(es)	Institute / Organisation	Land	Research-Role	Alias
06.03.2023, 09:00	Phone Call	Jürg von Deschwanden*	Forensisches Institut Zürich, Fachgruppe Dokumente	Switzerland	Doc Expert	DE01
06.03.2023, 11:00	Online meeting	Jörg Aehnlich*	Bundeskriminalamt, Kriminaltechnik Urkunden & Ausweissysteme	Germany	Doc Expert	DE02
08.03.2023, 11:00	Online meeting	Marcel Schafroth	Bundesamt für Zoll und Grenzsicherheit BAZG	Switzerland	Doc Expert	DE03
08.03.2023, 17:00	Online meeting	redacted	Home Office, His Majesty's Passport Office	United Kingdom	Doc Expert	DE04
09.03.2023, 09:00	Airport Zurich, in Person	David Squindo	Kantonspolizei Zürich, Flughafen	Switzerland	Doc Expert	DE05
11.03.2023, 10:00	Online meeting	redacted	Landespolizeidirektion Niederösterreich	Austria	Doc Expert	DE06
16.03.2023, 13:00	Online meeting	C. T.	Kantonspolizei Bern	Switzerland	Doc Expert	DE07
March 2023	Written Contribution	redacted	State Border Guard Service	Ukraine	Doc Expert	DE08
15.03.2023, 09:00	Online meeting	Franz Zeier	Landespolizeidirektion Niederösterreich, Autobahnpolizei	Austria	Doc Expert	DE09
07.03.2023, 11:00	Online meeting	Michael Morenz*	Landesamt für Ausbildung, Fortbildung und Personalangelegenheiten der Polizei Nordrhein-Westfalen	Germany	Front Policing	PP01
08.03.2023, 10:00	Online meeting	redacted	UK Border Force	United Kingdom	Front Policing	PP02
08.03.2023, 12:00	Online meeting	redacted	Bundesamt für Zoll und Grenzsicherheit BAZG	Switzerland	Front Policing	PP03
09.03.2023, 10:00	Airport Zurich, in Person	L. W.	Kantonspolizei Zürich, Flughafen	Switzerland	Front Policing	PP04
17.03.2023, 10:00	Online meeting	Stefan Donner	Bundespolizeiinspektion Kriminalitätsbekämpfung	Germany	Front Policing	PP05

* Represents personal opinion, does not necessarily speak for the associated organization.

List of Interviews Held (Continued)

Date	Place	Interviewe(es)	Institute / Organisation	Land	Research-Role	Alias
17.03.2023, 10:00	Online meeting	Karsten Klenke	Bundeskriminalamt, Kriminaltechnik Urkunden & Ausweissysteme	Germany	Service Center	SC01
30.03.2023, 13:00	Online meeting	Jessica Luh-Fuchs	Document Authentication Services GmbH	Germany	Service Center	SC02
24.03.2023, 10:00	Online meeting	redacted	Bundespolizeidirektion Stuttgart, Gemeinsames Zentrum der deutsch-französischen Polizei- und Zollzusammenarbeit	Germany	Service Center	SC03
06.03.2023, 10:00	Online meeting	Silvia Lips	Estonian Information System Authority (NCSC-EE)	Estonia	Strategy/Exec	EX01
07.03.2023, 16:00	Online meeting	redacted*	Ministerie van Defensie	Netherlands	Strategy/Exec	EX02
16.03.2023, 20:00	Online meeting	Petros Tsiolas	Police Directorate of Kastoria, Security & Alien Office	Greece	Strategy/Exec	EX03
09.03.2023, 17:00	Online meeting	Marco Boscolo	Polizia Locale Venezia	Italy	Strategy/Exec	EX04
14.03.2023, 15:00	Online meeting	redacted	City of Amsterdam, Team Identiteitsfraude (TIF)	Netherlands	Strategy/Exec	EX05
09.03.2023, 18:00	Online meeting	Pavelas Staskevicius	State Border Guard Service	Lithuania	Strategy/Exec	EX06
16.03.2023, 09:30	Online meeting	Mathias Schaefer	Bundespolizeipräsidium Potsdam	Germany	Strategy/Exec	EX07
24.03.2023, 13.00	Online meeting	Ingo Alvermann	Bundespolizeipräsidium Potsdam	Germany	Strategy/Exec	EX08
March 2023	Written Contribution	redacted	Kyiv Scientific Research Institute of Forensic Expertise	Ukraine	Strategy/Exec	EX09
March 2023	Written Contribution	Media Team	Frontex	Poland	Strategy/Exec	EX10

* Represents personal opinion, does not necessarily speak for the associated organization.

Appendix G Recordings and Transcripts

The protection of the privacy of participants was important for me, given that they provide a lot of trust and somewhat internal information which could be misused if obtained by the wrong entities. Therefore, no transcripts are added to this document. Instead, the original media and transcripts are stored in an encrypted container with password protection. The password itself is stored in another password database not available for the public.

The data (or their key) remain available until 31.12.2023 and are deleted afterwards. Upon request, it is possible to obtain extracts of transcripts under the condition that the concerning participant provides consent.

The working file of the MAXQDA (which contain the coded transcripts) is provided to my supervisor, also in an encrypted and password protected version.

No copies of transcripts or recordings remain on any public platform or file storage

Figure 15 G Deletion of Recordings and Transcripts

Appendix H Statistics for Nerds

Figure 16 H Sum of Interview Durations

24 items, 17h 42m

Table 6 H Transcription Word Count

Document name	Coded Segments	Paragraphs	Sentences	Words	Characters
DE01	45	78	346	3'003	19'898
DE02	105	121	1'085	12'471	78'136
DE03	60	105	570	5'602	35'581
DE04	87	127	813	8'698	47'949
DE05	73	105	410	5'235	35'016
DE06	99	144	673	6'499	39'748
DE07	72	120	616	5'679	35'850
DE08	28	66	101	882	5'650
DE09	59	118	585	5'032	31'936
EX01	47	78	777	6'447	35'094
EX02	57	104	558	6'370	34'089
EX03	79	146	910	5'415	32'974
EX04	63	158	528	3'385	19'304
EX05	72	274	961	6'959	37'074
EX06	66	147	559	3'361	19'396
EX07	161	103	789	10'125	66'249
EX08	81	85	590	7'496	48'093
EX09	33	68	97	883	5'664
EX10	25	37	134	1'086	7'209
PP01	79	77	653	8'471	52'453
PP02	48	109	477	3'667	19'580
PP03	50	94	371	3'936	25'461
PP04	39	72	282	2'778	17'904
PP05	45	76	365	4'068	25'966
SC01	79	73	656	9'738	63'954
SC02	45	96	530	6'067	38'790
SC03	74	78	518	5'982	38'854
Total	1'771	2'859	14'954	149'335	917'872

Appendix I Inductive Literature Coding

I did an initial inductive coding while screening the books and came up with 22 codes. Each code was used between once and five times over all books (excluding online papers and journal articles which were consulted in a backwards- and forward search at a later stage).

Keyword	Platform Revolution	Machine Platform Crowd	The Platform Economy	Institutional Trust	Matchmakers	The Economics of Platforms	Work and Value Creation in the ...	TECHNOLOGY-DRIVEN TASK REPLACEMENT ...	The future of employment: How susceptible...	Number of mentions
Platform Definition / Types	x	x	x		x	x				5
Network Effects	x	x	x		x	x				5
Job of a Platform	x	x	x		x	x				5
Value Creation & Risks	x	x			x	x	x	x		4
Job of the Operator / Moderator / Manager	x	x			x	x				4
Trust			x	x	x	x				4
Problem: Chicken & Egg	x				x	x				3
Monetization / Value Capture	x				x	x				3
Theories			x		x					2
Expanding Use cases					x	x				2
Core Interaction	x									1
End-to-End Principle	x									1
Quality assurance	x									1
Openness	x									1
Processes & Automation		x					x			1
o2o transactions		x								1
Rollenteilung (core & crowd)		x								1
Devices / Access / Technology			x					x		1
Problem: Principle Agent				x						1
Problem: Collective Action					x					1
Matchmaking & Rating						x				1
Employment Impacts							x	x	x	

The inductive codes from the literature were later merged (subsumed) into the deductive coding by Özcan et al. This provided the final deductive category base, mixed with the existing codes, enriched through inductive “en vivo” and descriptive coding.

Final Coding for Interview

Value Prop

Governance (Openness)

Trust

Stakeholders

Strategy (Launch/Growth)

IT Architecture (Infra)

User Interface / Device

Pricing / Costs

Legislation and Regulation

Culture

Appendix J Deductive Categories with Inductive Codes

Category	(1) Governance (major success factor)
Description	This category contains codes that are related to the general governance and administration of the platform and includes general operational insights
Codes	
Code	Description
Desired Operator	Insights about the entity which should oversee managing the platform, its responsibilities and duties.
Approval and Sanctions	How new participants should be approved to the platform and what happens if the participant misconducts
Trust	Statements related to trust in foreign experts, organisations, or the platform itself
Internal Rules & Regulations	Insights about potential or existing rules and regulations for ongoing platform operations
Openness	Statements with insights about how open the platform can be, for example “limited to police” or “open to commercial entities”

Category	(2) Stakeholders (major success factor)
Description	This category contains codes that are related to stakeholders, participants, players in the industry, and the team
Codes	
Code	Description
Desired Participants	Entities that could participate on the platform on one or more sides of the platform, for example
Existing Entities	Companies or organisations that are currently involved in the topic of international ID authentication
Top-Mgmt Support	Statements which include hints towards the importance of support from the top management and head level, for a platform project or international collaboration to succeed
Management Team	Companies or organisations which do have some sort of management role or are seen as potential managers of the platform
Expected Stakeholders	Companies that are mentioned as stakeholder of a platform for document authentication or may be interested because of the context where they were mentioned
Undesired participants	Entities that were mentioned in a way which would not benefit the case or cause problems if included in the platform

Category	(3) Value Proposition (major success factor)
Description	This category contains codes which provide insights about the value proposition a platform could offer, including problems. Five core value propositions emerged through grouping during the analysis, with a last group of unsorted or not considered codes.
Codes	
Group 1: Processes, lead and wait time → Efficiency	
Code	Description
Process Steps	Statements which provide insights about how the processes of document authentication or collaboration
Lead / Wait Time	Statements about how long certain steps take
Desired Lead Time	Statements (mostly from police officers) about how long they can wait for a reply
Group 2: Education, training, and confidence → More Checks	
Code	Description
Education, Training & Experience	Statements about problems or opportunities with education, training and experience
Case: First assessment	Statements and opinions about a first assessment
Easier access leads to more checks	Statements about the consequences of easier access to experts
Group 3: Personal connections and finding the right person → Networking	
Code	Description
Personal Network	Statements where a participant mentioned his personal network and the connections made during their career used for ID authentication
Forge network / find People	Statements about the relevance of finding the right people (or problems caused by not finding them)
Group 4: Federalism, Redundancies → Harmonizing platforms	

Code	Description
Federalism	Statements about the challenge of different (cantonal/country specific) regulations, systems and possibilities
Harmonizing Systems	Mentions of Systems and similarities which could be connected or merged beneficially
Redundancies	Statements about similar activities taking place on different locations

Group 5: Language

Code	Description
Language	Language specific problems for interaction and collaboration

Other Codes:

Code	Description
International Collaboration	Statements about existing and the need for international collaboration
Value of remote Support	Statements about the value proposition of remote support
Technology Comparison	Data where technologies are rated to find out which technology would be most useful
Downsides and Challenges	Downsides and Challenges in platform-based collaboration
Usability / User Interface	Statements about benefits and challenges of different user interfaces
Desired opening hours	Statements which reveal discrepancies for opening hours
Sharing of Resources	Statements about benefits of sharing resources
Desired Functionality	Statements which reveal discrepancies for functionality
Desired interaction results	Statements which provide insights about results that should emerge from a collaboration

Category	(4) Strategic Management (major success factor)	
Description	This category contains codes that are related to strategic topic, management questions, launch, growth and approval	
Codes		
Code	Description	
Strategic Activities	Statements about planned, ongoing or previous strategic activities with relevance towards (platform based) remote document authentication	
Strategic Goals	Statements about the goal that should be achieved through the platform	
Most important interaction	Statements which provide insights about the most important interaction or functionality (to prioritize future use cases)	
First Mover / Early Adopter	Statements about the willingness to participate and support the development	
Launch & Growth	Hints about how a platform should be implemented in the market, and how it can be grown	
Prerequisites for Approval	Crucial prerequisites without which the platform can not be established	
KPIs	Any relevant facts and figures, which are important for executives or steering committees	
Driving Force	Statements hinting towards important entities (similar to stakeholders / management board)	

Category	(5) IT and Technology (minor success factor)	
Description	This category contains codes that are related to existing platforms, all kinds of devices, apps and networks	
Codes		
Code	Description	
Existing Platforms	Statements about existing platforms or systems that are relevant for (international) document authentication	
Devices Mobile	Mobile devices, potentially useful for platform-based collaboration, such as smartphones or tablets	
Devices Magnifiers, utilities and Tools	Statements about utilities around document authentication, such as light sources and magnifiers	
Devices Laptops or Computers	“less mobile devices” which offer more functionality, usually Microsoft based.	
Devices Forensic devices	Statements about microscopes or specific equipment for advanced document authentication	
Devices Missing or Desired	All data which provides information about devices which would be useful to have during document authentication	
Police Apps	Any apps which are designed, operated and deployed by any police (not available to the public)	
Public Apps	Any apps which are developed and provided by non-police organizations such as commercial entities	
Networking	Data about (data) networks from an IT perspective	

Category	(6) Marketing & Communication (minor success factor)	
Description	This category contains codes that are related to marketing and communication activities about products and or services related to document authentication.	
Codes		
	Code	Description
	Marketing & Communication	This code covers statements which relate to marketing and communication activities.

Category	(7) Culture (minor success factor)	
Description	This category contains codes that are related to the culture, personal mindsets, assessment of the company mindset, motivation and expected reactions	
Codes		
Code	Description	
Digital Readiness	Statements about or answers towards questions of digital readiness and the likelihood of interviewed members (or their team)	
Willingness to collaborate	Statements about the willingness to collaborate outside the own organisation or country, across different organisations, to receive or offer help	
Mindset towards ID authentication	Statements which shed light onto the (required/desired/different) mindsets in the context of document authentication	
(Staff) reaction and acceptance	Statements about the general acceptance of a platform, or (mainly from executives) about how they think their staff would react if a platform would be there.	

Category	(8) Pricing & Business Model (minor success factor)	
Description	This category contains codes related to funding, cost distribution, payments, transactions, impact and current costs	
Codes		
Code	Description	
Split costs, fund development	All data related to funding of a platform, and how costs should be split between participants	
Inter-Orrg. Payments and transaction costs	A very important code to tag statements about transaction costs and how payments are settled between companies	
Impact of Payment	Statements which provide insights about what impact payment would have to individuals and departments or even organisations	
Current costs	Statements which provide insights about the current costs of ID authentication	

Category	(9) Legislation & Regulation (minor success factor)	
Description	This category contains codes related to legal and regulative data, especially data protection	
Codes		
Code	Description	
General Legal Framework	Data around the legal situation between countries or police organisations in general	
Data Protection	Statements about data protection, measures, controls, requirements and the current situation	
Usefulness of Censoring	Statements which shed light about the approach to distinguish between document authenticity checks and identification of people	
Liability Accountability	Statements which clarify how reliable statements from document experts are, if provided in person or through remote means such as phone, picture or helpdesk services	

Appendix K Intercoder Reliability

Intercoder reliability was assessed by asking André Gubser (my manager with similar experience) to code two short contributions of the study with a given set of codes. This activity aimed to improve coding because good coding (analysis) is the base for reliable results. The results were assessed over three perspectives.

Firstly, the existence of the codes within documents was assessed and showed that many codes were used in a similar way:

Table 7 K1 Intercoder Reliability - Existence

Dokumentname	Übereinstimmung	Nicht-Übereinstimmung	Prozentual
DE08_UA_20230324_0000	5	4	55.56
EX09_UA_20230331_0000	7	2	77.78
<Total>	12	6	66.67

Secondly, the frequency of codes was assessed and it was surprising that a discrepancy emerged from the analysis:

Table 8 K2 Intercoder Reliability - Frequency

Dokumentname	Übereinstimmung	Nicht-Übereinstimmung	Prozentual
DE08_UA_20230324_0000	2	7	22.22
EX09_UA_20230331_0000	2	7	22.22
<Total>	4	14	22.22

I lastly compared the consistency of coded segments, which revealed a devastating result. No coded segments aligned:

Table 9 K3 Intercoder Reliability - Segments

Code	Übereinstimmung	Nicht-Übereinstimmung	Prozentual
Current Problems	0	15	0.00
Value Proposition	0	38	0.00
Strategic Management	0	5	0.00
Governance	0	9	0.00
Stakeholders	0	4	0.00
Pricing & Business Model	0	6	0.00
Legislation & Regulation	0	8	0.00
IT and Technology	0	19	0.00
Culture	0	7	0.00
<Total>	0	111	0.00

A closer look revealed that we generally associated similar codes to similar segments. The discrepancy could be explained by a different coding style because André Gubser tended to code on a more granular way than myself (which is not surprising given the fact that the two documents only represented 1.2% of all data processed through me).

Figure 17 K1 Coding Style: A. Gubser

Figure 18 K2 Coding Style: S. Gabriel

This intercoder reliability check had a positive impact on the analysis of data and thus improved the credibility and reliability of the results, conclusions, discussion, and recommendation.

Appendix L Declaration of Sole Authorship

I, Stefan Gabriel, hereby certify that the attached work, Degree Dissertation "Can Platform-Based International Police Collaboration Simplify the Authentication of Identity Documents?", is wholly and completely my own and that I have indicated all the sources (printed, electronic, personal, etc.) that I have consulted. Any sections quoted from these sources are clearly indicated in quotation marks or are otherwise so declared. I further attest that I have included acknowledgement of the name(s) of any person(s) consulted in the course of preparing this assignment.